

Making CCU and CCS Hubs and Clusters Happen – Overcoming Non-Technical Challenges

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WP Leader or co-leader	Matthias Honegger		27.05.2024
Project Coordinator	Eirik Falk da Silva		19.6.2024

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Authorship

This white paper is co-authored by the following individuals whereby the names are ordered by organisations and the order of naming them is no indication of their levels of involvement:

Matthias Honegger; Soyoung Oh; Florian Schmitt; Matthias Poralla (Perspectives Climate Research)

Lena W. Østgaard, Ingvild Ombudstvedt (IOM Law)

Romain Viguier, Erika Palfi, Rebecca Bell, Darrick Evensen, Hannah Chalmers (SCCS, University of Edinburgh)

Farid Karimi; Ulrika Dahlberg (University of Jyväskylä)

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Executive Summary

Successful development of CCU and CCS hubs and clusters is as much a technological challenge as it is a non-technical challenge. Non-technical challenges span social and political aspects, economics, monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV), as well as legal, regulatory, and contractual aspects. Many of these can become showstoppers if they are not given due careful attention by the partners involved in the development and delivery of CCU and CCS hubs and clusters.

While non-technical challenges tend not to predetermine success, they represent malleable and dynamic factors that evolve over time in response to broader changes. Such changes can occur in public narratives, national politics, local planning processes, or regulatory requirements and policy-induced financial support. These can flow to the financial bottom line, and all influence the question whether a particular CCUS endeavour ultimately shows a financially sustainable business case – unlocking the required capital – or not.

Attending to non-technical challenges – particularly through proactive measures (e.g., engaging with regulators, local populations, and civil society organisations) requires time, which unless planned for carefully – alongside engineering and business development efforts – may add to and delay operationalisation through the stages of scoping, planning, and implementation. This white paper addresses some of the most prominently discussed challenges across the various non-technical areas identified in the first part of the project CCUS ZEN. It also discusses their relevance for future CCUS hubs and clusters in the Baltic Sea region as well as the Mediterranean.

Key social and political challenges

Limited awareness and can undermine social acceptance of CCUS among publics, especially concerning underground CO₂ storage, but awareness and support appears to grow in many countries. Carbon capture and use (CCU) is occasionally perceived more beneficially. The apparent gap in the knowledge and information available to the public and policymakers represents a significant risk to medium-term public support for large CCUS public infrastructure projects. Public-facing communication on CCUS may require additional measures beyond science-public information flows offering simplified messages: A more involved, comprehensive, early, and recurring engagement may be recommended as in similar areas of climate-relevant public infrastructure projects (e.g. geothermal energy) that may be perceived as risky or otherwise problematic. Disseminating bite-sized information through multiple public-facing channels can help if they come from credible sources, offer transparency, and frame CCUS as a necessary yet modest part of a comprehensive climate strategy. Mistrust towards politicians and policymakers as well as towards large industry players can undermine efforts. These may, therefore, not be ideal communicators for CCUS projects. Instead, research institutions and NGOs enjoy trust both in the Baltic Sea and the Mediterranean regions may thus be helpful communicating science-based and accessible information on CCUS to enhance the public basis for well-deliberated and reasoned acceptance of CCUS related (public) investments and construction projects.

Acceptance may also be influenced by the required infrastructures, whereby transport often poses a challenge, whether flowing from the siting and construction of pipelines or from the environmental disturbance posed by trucking or rail transport.

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The political landscape of objectives and associated policies is also shifting, notably through the introduction of the European Carbon Management Strategy and the Net-zero Industry Act, which provide some orientation as to where the European Union might be headed and what CCUS activities may be targeted for dedicated support. The envisaged phase out of fossil fuel consumption may affect the future range and volume of CO₂ sources requiring capture and storage.

Key economic and carbon accounting related challenges

The viability of CCUS technologies hinges on overcoming significant economic and financial hurdles. These include the development of business models that can attract sustained investment without direct product output, addressing financial and cross-chain risks in pioneering projects, and creating market demand through policy and standards. Preventing the relocation of polluting economic activity (so-called carbon leakage) (perhaps through mechanisms like the EU's Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism) may help maintain industry competitiveness. The transport modalities and distances of CO₂ transport rank high among the factors for economic efficiency. Success depends on innovative financial strategies, government interventions, and international cooperation to navigate these economic complexities and realize the potential of CCUS within the climate change mitigation portfolio.

The IPCC guidelines for national greenhouse gas (GHG) inventories do offer some direction regarding the accounting of results from carbon capture, transport, and storage at the national level. However, they fall short of clearly addressing how to report results from emerging carbon dioxide removal methods: In case of bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS), ambiguities regarding the sustainability of biomass and the accounting of harvested wood products can be cause for confusion. In case of direct air capture and storage (DACs, see section 1.4) it is unclear in which (sub-)sector it may be reported.

For project-specific monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV) a broad range of methodologies are currently emerging and CCS or CCU based carbon projects have not yet entered the world of carbon markets. While internationally there are MRV methodologies (mainly in voluntary carbon markets) for carbon capture and storage that may serve for inspiration, there remains a palpable void regarding comprehensive guidance that would allow tracking the results across complex CCUS hubs and clusters. Consistent application of additionality and baseline setting will be crucial for long-term credibility of CCUS and its long-term access to carbon revenue especially where carbon markets and subsidies interact. Awareness of MRV requirements and broader carbon market expectations is limited among CCUS stakeholders.

Key legal challenges

Diversity and inconsistency mark the landscape of national regulatory frameworks for CCS and CCU, as they are at varied stages and possess different levels of maturity especially concerning carbon dioxide storage permitting pursuant to the CCS Directive. Additionally, the permissibility for CO₂ storage varies, creating a need for cross-border collaboration for CCS for several countries. For Contracting Parties of the London Protocol, there is an imperative to provisionally apply the 2009 Amendment to Article 6 if they seek to export CO₂ for offshore storage. This necessitates the formulation of an arrangement or agreement in alignment with the Protocol's criteria. The stipulations vary depending on whether the CO₂ export is between two Contracting Parties or if it is from a Contracting Party to a non-Contracting Party. The Helsinki Convention presents a clear ban on CO₂ storage in the Baltic Sea. In contrast, the

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Barcelona Convention introduces a complex scenario with its two dumping protocols. While the initial Protocol might permit CO₂ storage, its subsequent amended Protocol does not. With the latter not being in force at the time of documentation, questions arise regarding legal obligations.

The European Commission is developing a comprehensive policy and regulatory framework relevant for CCU, facilitating for CO₂ being used in feedstock or resource for products such as polymers, building materials, chemicals and synthetic fuels, and services. There is no one-stop instrument for CCU. Instead, provisions may be found in a series of instruments such as the Renewable Energy Directive, the ETS and Monitoring and Reporting Regulations, the proposed Carbon Removal Certification Framework, and the newly introduced ReFuelEU Aviation and Fuel EU Maritime. These instruments provide both incentives and a push for Member States to implement both targets and frameworks to take CCU technologies into use to reduce emissions and replace fossil fuels with renewables, and further provide for methodology for reporting.

Summary of Recommendations

CCUS faces significant non-technical challenges including in some cases intersecting issues of regulatory, MRV, and accounting clarity of responsibility and the resulting coordination through private contracts between value-chain partners, particularly when dealing with cross-border CO₂ transfers. This is further complicated in case of pursuing revenue from international carbon markets other than the EU ETS, where the responsibility for addressing reversals remains to be clarified. Bilateral state agreements between involved countries and private contracts which mirror relevant structures seem to be a critical starting point for advancing clarity and defining responsibilities to report and address any leakage or reversal among capturing and storing entities as well as regulatory entities of the involved states. Progress in that realm should be proactively communicated also to broader publics to highlight the climate benefits of CCUS in each individual case.

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1 Introduction

This white paper is the result of a year-long process of mapping non-technical issues for the sighting and development of CCUS hubs and clusters in the Baltic and Mediterranean areas. It draws on previous work through a review of the literature and previous project findings and survey and workshop of project and network partners.

1.1 Categories of non-technical challenges

Developing multiple regional Carbon Capture, Utilisation, and Storage (CCUS) value chains to decarbonise industry and deliver negative emissions is a crucial and urgent task for the European Union. However, successfully achieving this goal involves more than just technical challenges. CCUS value chains involve multiple technologies and stakeholders in various industries, such as energy, transport, and CO₂ storage. These stakeholders must work together effectively to ensure the success of the CCUS value chains. In addition, many of these value chains may not have a clear business case without dedicated policy support, which must be developed and adapted in parallel with the technology.

One of the key challenges in implementing CCUS value chains is acceptance by the public and various stakeholders. Ensuring that the benefits of CCUS are understood and that the technology is perceived as safe and reliable will be crucial to gaining acceptance and support for the roll-out of CCUS value chains throughout Europe.

Another challenge is the economics of CCUS. While the long-term benefits of reducing greenhouse gas emissions are clear, the upfront costs of implementing CCUS technology can be significant. Developing policies and financial mechanisms to support the deployment of CCUS technology and ensure that it is economically viable will be essential to its success.

Ensuring the accuracy and reliability of emissions data is another key challenge, known as Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV). Similarly, consistent accounting of results in national greenhouse gas (GHG) inventories is needed. These two elements are key to track progress and ensure compliance with emissions reduction targets, but also to build confidence in the technology and support the development of effective policy.

Finally, legal challenges must also be addressed. Developing a clear legal framework for the implementation and operation of CCUS value chains will be crucial to ensuring their success. This may include establishing or operationalising regulations and standards for the storage of CO₂, as well as addressing issues related to liability and ownership of the stored CO₂ variously through public and private agreements.

Overall, addressing these challenges and ensuring coordination and collaboration among stakeholders will be crucial to the roll-out of CCUS value chains throughout Europe. Through the non-technical mapping of issues, CCUS ZEN Work Package 2 may make a modest contribution to that end.

1.2 Approach to issue-mapping and sources of data

The mapping of non-technical issues commenced with the creation of issue profiles, which were primarily grounded in expert knowledge and a review of relevant literatures. This provided a clear direction, terminology, and a framework for the subsequent stages. Following this, a survey was conducted – first among project partners – to gain complementary

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perspectives and insights on the issues identified as well as to ensure that no further non-technical issues were overlooked. This was further augmented by surveying network partners in industry in a second step, ensuring that the characterisation of challenges was based on stakeholders' real-world observations of non-technical challenges.

To further enrich the understanding and to encourage interactive discussions, three workshop-style webinars were organised. These interactions, which included expert presentations and breakout-group discussions with participants from project partners and network partners allowed us to capture key reactions and feedback. These webinars provided real-time insights and presented an opportunity for spontaneous discourse, also strengthening the shared understanding of key concepts among stakeholders. In addition, interviews were conducted with key actors who possessed a deeper understanding of region-specific challenges and opportunities. Their first-hand experiences and expert opinions added depth to the data collected by complementing evidence offered in a generalised manner in the literature with real-world anecdotal evidence also relating to ongoing developments. This white paper represents a synthesis of insights from all the above sources and viewpoints above.

1.3 Focus regions

The two regions that are in focus in CCUS ZEN overall – and thus also in this white paper – are A) the Baltic Sea region, including particularly Denmark, Sweden, and Germany, while also considering Poland and Finland and B) the Mediterranean region particularly including Spain and France, as well as Italy, Greece, and Turkey. These two focus regions and the particularities of the listed countries are examined in section 6.

1.4 Terminological Consistency

The successful collaboration across different disciplines, industries, and government departments requires a shared understanding of key concepts and terminologies. To advance such a shared understanding of key terms regarding CCUS, we put forward the following differentiation of terms, which we use throughout this report:

Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) refers to the capture of CO₂ at a point source followed by durable storage – most often underground in geological formations, exploited oil and gas fields, in basaltic rock formations, or in other similar sites.

Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage (CCUS) refers to the capture of CO₂ at a point source followed by utilisation in a long-lived and durable product, which thus achieves storage that is from a climate mitigation viewpoint essentially equivalent to geological storage. CCUS can also be used as an umbrella term to describe both CCS and CCU (as is the case for the project name (CCUS ZEN)).

Carbon Capture and Utilisation (CCU) refers to capture of CO₂ at a point source followed by utilisation in a short-lived product. This approach is excluded from our considerations, though it can under some circumstances help lower emissions by displacing more polluting alternatives (e.g. aviation fuels).

Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) refers to those measures that achieve (over their full lifecycle) a net removal of CO₂ from the atmosphere into durable storage. Those CCS and CCUS value-chains that process sustainable biomass (through so-called bioenergy with

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carbon capture and storage, BECCS) or CO₂ directly captured from ambient air (so-called Direct Air Capture and Storage, DACS) can achieve such a removal.

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2 Social and Political Aspects

2.1 Social aspects

Technology and technical knowledge of capturing, storing, and utilising carbon is constantly developing. Likewise, attitudes towards the technologies and policies change over time, and cannot be described as static. There are, however, some common social and political factors that affect social acceptance and engagement in local CCUS and CCS projects. Most laypeople do not reflect on how industry should be decarbonised and are not very familiar with the technology or the differences between CCS, CCU, CCUS. The growing consideration of carbon dioxide removals (see section 1.4) including via DACS and BECCS can lead to further confusion. However, public understanding has been increasing slowly during the last two decades. There is potential for targeted communication, bearing in mind that more knowledge does not always mean more acceptance.

2.1.1 Social acceptance

Social acceptance of CCUS and CCS means that stakeholders, including laypeople, are not actively opposing the technology. Lack of social acceptance has proven to be a critical factor in the implementation of the technology and establishment of storage sites. In the past, resistance from society has led to cancellation of projects, in e.g., the Netherlands (Akerboom *et al.* 2021, Terwel *et al.* 2012, Witte 2021) and Germany (Inderberg and Wettestad 2015). Societal engagement with CCUS and CCS and knowledge of its importance for climate change mitigation is, in many countries, very limited and civil society organisations have actively lobbied against CCUS and CCS in the past, especially when CCUS and CCS was presented as an option to decarbonise fossil fuel-based energy infrastructures (Karimi and Komendantova 2017). Investment and siting decisions related to carbon capture, storage and utilisation are affected by the public and stakeholders' reactions (Oltra *et al.* 2022).

Most research about acceptance of CCUS and CCS has focused on the general public. Perceptions among laypeople, politicians and experts could, however, all be affected by common cultural denominators (Karimi 2021). This could explain similar patterns of risk perceptions, regardless of differences in the level of expertise and knowledge between these groups. Thrifty, uncertainty avoidant, hierarchical societies tend to have a higher risk perception when it comes to CCUS and CCS. One example of this is Germany, where relatively homogenous and strong opposition against CCUS and CCS exists both among experts and laypeople. In contrast, Norway and Finland represent societies where risk perceptions of CCUS and CCS are low among experts and laypeople (Whitmarsh *et al.* 2019). These countries have relatively low-hierarchical, non-thrifty and low uncertainty-avoidance cultures (Karimi 2021). Risk and benefit perceptions are major factors in social acceptance of CCUS and CCS (L'Orange Seigo *et al.* 2014, Tcvetkov *et al.* 2019, Witte 2021).

Strongly related to cultural factors, trust is another major influence on public attitudes towards CCUS and CCS. Trust in institutional actors responsible for implementing or regulating projects is regularly revealed as the most important factor that shapes both risk and benefit perceptions (Otto and Gross 2021, Parmiter and Bell 2020). Trust reliably has a much larger effect on risk and benefit perceptions than knowledge of CCUS and CCS does (Evensen 2022). Of course, this relationship might change in the future as aggregate knowledge of CCUS and of CCS increase. On the community level, trust in stakeholders, such as

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governments, increases the acceptance of CCUS and CCS (Moon *et al.* 2020). Higher trust in stakeholders leads to lower risk perception. Using trusted sources – particularly scientific experts and especially people who are themselves local, or who have tangible local connections, is highly effective (Coyle 2016, Ferguson, and van Gent 2017). It seems trust in governments and industry in the Nordic countries is higher (Rodriguez *et al.* 2021) compared to the rest of Europe, particularly the Mediterranean Sea region (Oltra *et al.* 2022). Although there are clearly cultural and national differences in the level of trust in institutional actors, appropriate, laconic, transparent, pro-active, and intelligible messaging about the full range of risks and benefits is seen as essential for forthright communication and for building trust (de Vries 2016, de Vries *et al.* 2017, Kubota and Shimota 2017).

Honesty and comprehensively covering all aspects of a project and potential conflicts of interest is essential to avoid loss of trust at later stages (Terwel 2015). Two-way communication, as opposed to just distributing information, is viewed as essential for: building trust, benefiting from public input, and being able to update a project's communication strategy over time (Buhr and Wibeck 2014). Public awareness and specific knowledge about CCUS vary cross-nationally and regionally within countries, with higher acceptance in areas with a higher exposure to industrial projects, or prominent government policy on planning of projects (Broecks *et al.* 2021, Whitmarsh *et al.*, 2019). Acceptance of CCUS offshore and onshore can differ within the same country or region. Although offshore CCUS is sometimes more easily accepted, i.e., not actively resisted, it does not mean that it is actively supported. This leaves the potential effect of social support uncertain (Akerboom *et al.* 2021, Gough *et al.* 2017, Mabon *et al.* 2015).

More information does not *per se* lead to higher acceptance: Even when information has been associated with higher acceptance, the magnitude of the effect has been small (Whitmarsh *et al.* 2019). More information will not necessarily change local publics' views (Leiss and Larkin 2019) because those views tend to flow not from an understanding of the technical details, but from cultural associations and locally specific experiences. In some cases, additional information marginally increased support for CCUS or CCS. In others, it even decreased support, or had no effect (L'Orange Seigo *et al.* 2014): Top-down expert information tends to have very little practical effect on people's values and actions. In short: a project developer should not try to change public opinions through information, but rather to adopt inclusive practices that values and engages with the public opinions (Heberlein 2012).

Rather than a function of technical understandings, perceptions of risk and benefit of CCUS and CCS are shaped by culture, public awareness, and trust in the communicators involved in the project. Risk and benefit perceptions are inversely linked as ultimate determinants of support. When asked about benefits and risks of national and spatially distant CCUS activities, interviewees prioritized perceived benefits and inadvertently use such perception to shape perceived risk. Risk beliefs are more important factors in acceptance in cases of local and spatially close projects (Evensen 2022).

Research on public perceptions of CCUS or CCS often examines beliefs about risks and benefits attributed to the technology and its implementation (Tcvetkov *et al.* 2019). Table 1 presents risks and benefits most often cited by respondents – across numerous studies.

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Table 1: Frequently cited risks, concerns, and benefits among the public

<p>Concern: CCUS only addressing symptoms of problematic carbon emissions and not the causes.</p> <p>Risk: Incentivisation of CCUS leading to reduced policy incentives to mitigate carbon emissions further (“mitigation deterrence”)</p>	<p>Cox <i>et al.</i> 2020; Bellamy 2022</p>
<p>Concern: Safety concerns over physical leaks of CO₂ or explosions due to over-pressurisation</p> <p>Concern: Physical uncontrollability of the technology</p> <p>Risk: Public and scientific uncertainty about the technology</p>	<p>Broecks <i>et al.</i> 2021</p>
<p>Risk: High cost/expenses of the technology resulting in public expenditure or rising product prices</p>	<p>Karimi and Komendantova 2017</p>
<p>Benefit: Reducing carbon emissions, thereby mitigating climate change</p>	<p>Cox <i>et. al</i> 2020; Karimi <i>et al.</i> 2016;</p>
<p>Benefit: Economic investment in jobs and communities where projects occur</p>	<p>Satterfield <i>et al.</i> 2023</p>

A common concern is that, compared to mitigation, CCS only treats the symptoms and not the cause of climate change. Although it seems debatable whether keeping GHGs out of the atmosphere by capturing it at its source (or drawing CO₂ out of the atmosphere through BECCS or DACS) is in fact treating the symptoms or the cause, CCUS is viewed by vocal climate governance actors as an excuse – a means of holding on to unsustainable patterns of production and consumption and inequality between the global north and south (Cox *et al.* 2018). These critiques arose again in a prominent fashion during UNFCCC COP28 in Dubai in December 2023, due to the heavy focus on *unabated* fossil fuel emissions at that event.

Despite most research attention on social reactions to CCUS being focused on capture or storage, some scholarship has specifically examined CCU. Although more than ten academic citations are offered below on perceptions of CCU, the vast majority of these come from only two research groups. In an early review of the emergent research in this area, Jones *et al.* (2017b) present three dimensions related to CCU acceptance: socio-political, market, and community. Whilst most research in this area suggests marginal support for CCU, it is not clear how reliable these findings are, due to the extreme lack of awareness of what CCU is amongst the general public. Perdan *et al.* (2017) show awareness of CCU amongst a UK survey population at 9%. This lack of awareness and presence of misconceptions of what CCU is (indeed, even misconceptions of what CO₂ is) is further evidenced in in-depth interviews in the UK and Germany (Jones *et al.* 2017a, Offerman-van Heek 2017). The acceptance of CCU that does exist is, like CCUS and CCS, predicted by risk and benefit perceptions (Arning *et al.* 2018, 2019, 2020) and trust in relevant institutional actors (Offerman-van Heek *et al.* 2018). Some scholars have contended that the public views CCS

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as less beneficial compared to CCU, which also translates into higher perceived risk (Oltra *et al.* 2022). Risks associated with storage and transportation of carbon dioxide is one explanation (Glanz *et al.* 2021), yet the source of such perceptions may also relate to wording, whereby “utilisation” inherently suggests utility, whereas “storage” does not convey a sense of utility. Nevertheless, Olfe-Kräutlein *et al.* (2022) identify inconsistent terminology and technical descriptions of CCU as one potential cause of confusions and misunderstandings of CCU, which can decrease acceptance. Lutzke and Arvai (2021) bring some nuance to the market acceptance aspect of CCU, with research revealing that consumers are strongly opposed to using CCU for certain products (e.g., carbonated beverages), but that over two-thirds of their sample were willing to purchase at least one type of product made via CCU, amongst four diverse product types.

Perception is evolving along with common narratives and framings. This can be observed where categories and common associations are changing. An example of this is the category of carbon dioxide removal (CDR, see section 1.4), which partly overlaps with CCUS: CCUS can achieve CDR when the CO₂ originates from sustainable biomass or from direct air capture (DAC). Yet, “anthropogenic removals” have long been understood to relate exclusively to forestry and ecosystem-related sink enhancement. In recent years this category has, however, expanded to include removals achieved through technology often involving geological storage. On the other hand, a different discourse focussed on the terminology of “geoengineering” – deliberate large-scale interventions in the climate system – has also been associated with novel methods for achieving removal of CO₂ (Honegger, Burns, and Morrow, 2021). This framing – given the undefined notion of large-scale – is associated with exacerbated perceptions of risk and very low levels of acceptance (Cummings, Lin, and Trump, 2017).

Local opposition is often referred to as *NIMBY* – not in my backyard (Saito *et al.* 2019, Wojakowski *et al.* 2022). However, researchers studying public acceptance of infrastructure such as CCS facilities do not recommend adopting such a simplistic description from which acceptance derives (Devine-Wright 2011): People local to a project have awareness of local issues affected by the project in a manner that outside project developers do not (Braun 2017). Local publics also make different (cultural) associations e.g., with prior experiences in infrastructures, which can evoke comparisons to previous industrial problems, accidents, or loss of trust in industrial or government actors that were essentially not good neighbours to local communities (Terwel and Daamen 2012, Williams *et al.* 2021). Finally, local concerns can be fuelled by unfair distribution of risks and benefits. Often, risks are perceived as affecting the local level, with benefits (e.g. climate protection or financial revenue) occurring to an outside actor, or in the abstract: nationally or globally (Gough *et al.* 2017).

In short: local publics have legitimate views that are formed in a different manner than the views of the project-developing actors. Failing to see and hear those views is likely to undermine a project’s acceptance and success.

2.1.2 Social acceptability and public engagement

Social acceptability is a combination of social acceptance and social support. Social acceptability (Batel *et al.* 2013) is a more democratic and socially inclusive concept than social acceptance, which is a top-down concept and mainly evaluates whether stakeholders and laypeople are not actively opposing or contesting a technology. Social acceptability can only be understood in context of the engagement of local communities in developing CCUS or CCS projects (Whitmarsh *et al.* 2019, Gough *et al.* 2018, Glanz and Schönauer 2021).

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As is also the case for renewable energy projects, local communities could, in theory, also initiate CCUS and CCS projects. However, it is a complex issue to engage local communities in CCUS and CCS projects cf. renewable energy, not least due to the high costs and liability questions (Parmiter and Bell 2020). It is thus questionable how a local community can benefit from CCUS and CCS projects directly. Perceptions of benefit vary with varying perception of climate action urgency and of economic/employment benefits (Broecks *et al.* 2021).

Several scholars suggest a need for public involvement at early stages of planning, not only after key decisions have been made (Ashworth *et al.* 2012, Coyle 2016, Kaiser *et al.* 2014, Mabon *et al.* 2015, 2017). Some even suggest engagement before any public announcement of the project to factor the local public's concerns into decision-making. Such an approach can be beneficial due to the perception of procedural fairness as well as for the opportunity for developers to identify locally specific obstacles before investing time and money (Brunsting *et al.* 2011, Greenberg and Gauvreau 2014, Vercelli and Lombardi 2009). Nevertheless, ter Mors and van Leeuwen (2023) caution that public input must be considered in decision making processes; their data reveals that 'pseudo voice opportunity can be equally detrimental as giving no voice opportunity at all'. The tools for such involvement are (Otto and Gross 2021):

- social site characterisation,
- stakeholder mapping (Steeper 2013)
- and surveys.

By proactively listening to the voices of local publics through these activities at the earliest stage the project developer can better understand locally specific risks and opportunities and lessen risks of local opposition.

Clear communication with the public via multiple interactive channels is key (Otto and Gross 2021). The main tools for this are (Broecks *et al.* 2016, Coyle 2016, Leiss and Larkin 2019, Whitmarsh *et al.* 2019):

- focus groups,
- public broadcasting,
- deliberative workshops,
- proactively working with traditional media (Ferguson and van Gent 2017),
- adept use of social media (Szzybalski *et al.* 2014),
- and an accessible and relevant website (Feldpausch-Parker and Peterson 2015, Shimada *et al.* 2013).

Proactive rather than reactive communication is seen as essential for establishing positive attitudes towards a project (Löfstedt 2015); a project developer merely reacting to negative conceptions that have already formed will not win over the local publics. Proactively correcting 'misunderstandings before they become too ingrained' is also required from the beginning (Otto and Gross 2021).

2.2 Political aspects

Unlike public awareness of CCUS and CCS and general levels of social acceptability, which have been consistent, political reactions and policy-level support have fluctuated notably (Lipponen *et al.* 2017). This can be problematic for CCUS and CCS projects because major public investments and stable regulatory environments are a necessary condition for large-scale projects. Funding line cancellations and policy pivots can undermine confidence to a

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prohibitive degree. Strongly supportive government rhetoric and actions accelerating well-coordinated implementation strategies and implementation of transparent funding frameworks have all been present in successful cases in the past (Gough and Mander, 2022).

2.2.1 Political support

In a review of factors affecting political orientations to CCUS and CCS, Lipponen and colleagues (2017) offer the following as key drivers of political support: (1) contributes to long-term climate goals, (2) supports energy security in countries with strategic interest in continued fossil fuel use, (3) opens new markets and economic opportunities through leadership in CCUS and CCS technology innovation, and (4) offers local economic benefits related to preserving industries and job retention. Factors driving lack of political support for CCUS and CCS have been summarised as (Lipponen *et al.* 2017): (1) public opposition, (2) perceived competition with renewable technologies, (3) concerns of NGOs who are opposed to fossil fuel use, (4) project-specific challenges (including project timeframes and high operating and capital costs), and (5) concerns about historical ‘failure’ rates of CCUS and CCS projects (projects that were initiated, but did not reach completion). Romasheva and Ilinova (2019), in a systematic review of literature on a wide range of factors conditioning CCUS and CCS project success, point to 18 political and legal factors – ranging from domestic and international climate and energy policies, to taxes, tax credits and emissions trading, to state funding, R&D support, to predictable legal and permitting frameworks (see also Waller *et al.* 2020 on these governance points).

2.2.2 Evolving political support levels

Currently, two main factors have been changing the political landscape vis-à-vis CCUS and CCS in Europe: meeting the climate goals set by the EU and war in Ukraine. Some of the major European countries are lagging in meeting the climate goals; hence, seemingly, they need to consider all possible alternatives (Kurmayer 2023). Furthermore, after the Russian invasion of Ukraine, the whole process of the energy transition in Europe is under shadow for the seemingly mid-term, while the approach to energy security and security of supply needs to be revisited. In this light, CCUS and CCS is going to receive more attention as an option to secure energy supply from undesired alternatives like fossil fuels for the short-term and biomass, while curbing CO₂ emissions. Currently, several countries in Europe, such as a couple of the Nordics (WSCO 2022, Government Offices of Sweden 2020) (e.g., Sweden and Denmark), Baltic States (Ulmanis and Zvirgzdiņa 2021) and Poland (Fabiszewska-Solares *et al.* 2021; Bieliszczuk 2021), have revisited their policies against CCUS and CCS. These countries are gradually shifting towards supporting CCUS and CCS to reduce their CO₂ emissions while securing supply.

2.3 Regional aspects of social and political readiness to implement CCUS: Mediterranean region vs. the Baltic Sea region

Based on a thorough literature review, a survey of stakeholders and an expert workshop, we have estimated the level of public acceptance and political development in the Mediterranean countries and the countries of the Baltic Sea region (Table 2).

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Table 2: Public acceptance and political development in the Baltic Sea and the Mediterranean regions

COUNTRY	PUBLIC ACCEPTANCE	POLITICAL DEVELOPMENT
Denmark (BAL)	Medium	Favourable
Estonia (BAL)	Medium	Business as usual
Finland (BAL)	Medium	Business as usual
Germany (BAL)	Low	Business as usual
Latvia (BAL)	Medium	Business as usual
Lithuania (BAL)	Low	Unfavourable
Poland (BAL)	Low	Favourable
Sweden (BAL)	Medium	Favourable
France (MED)	Low	Favourable
Greece (MED)	Low	Business as usual
Italy (MED)	Low	Unfavourable
Spain (MED)	Medium	Business as usual
Turkey (MED)	Medium	Business as usual

Three parameters were chosen for public acceptance: high, medium, and low (although no country was identified as high in acceptance), and three for political development: favourable, business as usual, and unfavourable, where business as usual means no change due to the Russian invasion of Ukraine or EU climate goals. The most interesting countries for further research could be those with low cohesion between social acceptance and political developments, such as France and Poland, where public acceptance is low and political developments are favourable.

The discussion in the CCUS ZEN WP2 workshop on social and political issues supported the statement that trust in governments and industry is higher in the Nordic countries than in the Mediterranean countries. This affects the implementation of CCUS and CCS projects and defines who should do the communication and how. Examples from Denmark show that high trust in the government makes communication relatively easy and that information has a positive effect on acceptance. Municipalities, local politicians, and companies are involved in outreach and communication with the locals. However, there are micro-cultural differences between northern and southern parts of the country, which affect acceptance, and city-countryside polarisation. Perceived risks by the public are health issues, or even the risk of death because of CO₂ leakages and accidents, decreased property value, and regarding offshore CCS, a negative impact on the ocean scenery and fishery. In general, the Danish example of mobilising local politicians to communicate and engage with local communities has gone well and built trust between stakeholders. Therefore, there are some lessons here to be learnt for other countries.

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When it comes to political development, the discussion confirmed that the developments in both regions (the Baltic and the Mediterranean) are mostly in favour of the large-scale deployment of CCUS and CCS, especially for industries like steel and cement. In countries like Denmark, Germany and Poland, the political landscape vis-à-vis CCS has changed significantly in the positive direction.

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3 Markets, MRV, and Accounting

3.1 Economic Aspects of CCUS

In economic terms, CCUS represents the internalisation of an economic externality. So, in many ways, economic aspects bring together all other dimensions of the CCUS challenge insofar that the business model that needs to be demonstrated to mobilise investments requires overcoming all other potential obstacles – technological as well as non-technical.

Other economic issues include potential challenges flowing from CCUS' positioning and interaction with other mitigation efforts requiring resources and political attention, the complexity of CCUS value chains requiring appropriate institutional solutions, planning processes involved in permitting of installations in marine and land spaces, and storage related liability costs.

Furthermore, the scarcity of mature storage sites presents a nuanced economic challenge, particularly affecting projects in regions distant from established facilities, a factor acknowledged but not detailed herein. This scarcity underscores the critical need for strategic planning and investment to identify and develop new storage capacities, ensuring the long-term viability of CCUS projects.

3.1.1 The Emissions Trading System (ETS) Relevance to CCUS

One of the main financial incentives for CCUS may be found in the European Trading System (ETS), regulated under the ETS Directive (Directive 2003/87/EC). The ETS is imposing a cap-and-trade scheme for emissions, applicable to both onshore and offshore industries. The EU-wide cap is distributed according to annex II and is to be reduced over time. The allowed emissions (allowances) under the regime are subject to a price on CO₂, implying that even if the installation is permitted to emit CO₂, there is still a penalty. Certain industries have received a grace period of free allowances, to prevent carbon leakage. If one is unable to reduce one's emissions to fit the allocated allowances, one can buy excess allowances from installations that have managed to reduce the emissions to fit within the allowances, hence the cap and trade. If the installation emits more CO₂ than the predefined cap, without arranging for the purchase of allowances from the market, the installation will be subject to a financial penalty.

Approximately 40% of the emissions in the EU are comprised by the ETS regime. With the implementation of the CCS Directive in 2009, the ETS Directive was amended to include CCS in Annex I, plying both that emissions from CCS installations would have to be reported and surrendered allowances for and that CCS could be used as an approach to reduce emissions and thus avoid an obligation to surrender allowances from other activities.

The implementing regulation to the ETS Directive on the monitoring and reporting (MMR, 2018/2066) provides for the baseline for when an operator of an installation may subtract emissions from the installation. In Article 49, it is stated that emissions "transferred out of the installation" to a capture installation, transport network or storage site with the purpose to store the CO₂ geologically pursuant to the CCS Directive, "CO₂ originating from fossil carbon" may be subtracted from the emissions of the installation. CO₂ captured by an ETS installation can be transferred to another ETS installation for transport/storage. As long as the transferred CO₂ remains in installations or value chains recognised by the ETS, it does not matter whether the

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CO₂ crosses national borders or not. In 2023, the ETS Directive was amended to include means of transport other than pipelines (i.e. ship/truck), which thus also allows for such modes of transportation in a CCS value chain. The CCS Directive and the MRR were not amended to correspond to the updated ETS Directive, implying that Article 49 of the MRR still only allows for subtracting emissions transferred to “a transport network with the purpose of long-term geological storage in a storage site permitted under Directive 2009/31/EC” In Article 3(63) ‘transport network’ is defined as “transport network as defined in Article 3(22) of Directive 2009/31/EC”, which in Article 3(22) defines the same network as “the network of pipelines, including associated booster stations, for the transport of CO₂ to the storage site.” Thus, the EU regulatory framework for CCS value chains is still incomplete and inconsistent, which poses a challenge for the economic viability.

3.1.2 Challenges related to development of business models securing investments

CCS does not produce a ‘product’ in the traditional sense, so it requires government intervention to make it happen. This can be in the form of government ownership of projects, regulatory requirements, government funding or other measures (see GCCSI 2019 for more detail). Different approaches have their merits, but no country has yet found one that drives investment in CCS in the long term (after the end of any initial subsidy period / government investment) and prevents ‘carbon leakage’ from high-emitting industries moving overseas.

Carbon capture and storage can represent a very significant cost increase with varying shares of output between industries: high capture rate CCS add anywhere from +60% to +100% to the cost of making cement (IEA 2020, Kearns *et al.* 2021).

Specific issues include:

- The need to mitigate and underwrite cross-chain risks, which are particularly high for first-of-a-kind projects.
- The need for financial security to underwrite CO₂ storage permits.
- How to address both supply and demand: demand mechanisms could include certification of low-carbon products, accompanied by public procurement rules that require low-carbon materials to be used in major projects; alternatively, governments could set standards for carbon intensity of products.

The risk of carbon leakage due to emissions standards or a high carbon price (such as in the EU ETS) can be mitigated by a carbon border adjustment mechanism (CBAM) such as is being developed by the European Commission (European Commission 2023a). The EU CBAM will initially apply to cement, iron and steel, aluminium, fertilisers, electricity and hydrogen, and the transitional phase is due to begin in October 2023. The phasing in of the CBAM will align with the phasing out of free allocations in the EU ETS.

Stakeholders surveyed agreed that enabling all players to make a good business case was crucial. They suggested several ways of achieving this:

- Having clear economic incentives to realise projects
- EU or country level funding mechanisms
- More programs, and with higher budget, like Horizon Europe, the Connecting Europe Facility and the EU ETS Innovation Fund

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- Country or EU level compensation mechanisms must be put in place to mitigate the business exposure of the different parties in the value chain if another party underperforms
- Dedicated funding for each project scope. The need for integrated projects, with multiple players, hampers access to funding
- Temporary incentives/ funding of the gap between CO₂ taxes and cost of CCUS
- Access to low-cost capital
- Massive subsidising scheme for shared CO₂ infrastructure
- Allow and promote state-aid for the development of infrastructure
- Promotion of carbon contracts for difference (CCfDs).

Certainty is another important ask: stakeholders also wanted greater certainty on the price of CO₂ to be able to demonstrate a viable business case for investment in CCS projects; they also raised the issue that a change in government can mean changes to subsidy regimes, which make a long-term business case risky to allow certainty over future income. As well as the funding for projects, stakeholders raised the issue of partnership and ownership structures within projects.

3.1.3 Challenges related to interaction with other mitigation technologies

Development of CCUS clusters will not happen in a vacuum: at the same time as major CCUS capital and infrastructure projects, similarly large net zero-aligned project such as renewable energy, hydrogen infrastructure and oil and gas decommissioning will also be developed. These projects are likely to be in competition for resources, funding, and skilled workers, so long-term strategic planning is needed to ensure that all the activity that needs to happen to reach net zero can be done.

This includes:

- Developing production capacity, sites, and skilled workers
- Ensuring access to sufficient clean energy (particularly relevant for CO₂ utilisation)
- Understanding the timing and sequencing of big projects
- Where workers are expected to re-train or move sector, enabling a just transition.

CCUS hubs and clusters can be initiated by a variety of different types of actors, such as state entities, trade or dedicated local industry associations, group of major emitters, or oil and gas operators. The important thing is to have or gain the trust of the other parties to build momentum and bring everyone on board in a mutually beneficial and transparent manner. Stakeholders have highlighted the need for a framework that allows cooperation rather than promoting competition for funding. For example, the UK Government Cluster Sequencing Competition has selected the first two clusters to be developed in the UK, both in the north of England.

Related to this is a need for an industrial vision for carbon neutrality, particularly within clusters. By working together towards the goal of net zero, industries can benefit from economies of scale and provide reassurance to their supply chain about the ongoing need for products, services, and workers. Industries in a cluster that do not have a decarbonisation goal may find

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it hard to make the case to participate. There are tensions to be addressed between having enough transparency to effectively work together, realise cost-efficiency and avoid monopolies and windfall profits, and protecting competition and trade secrets.

Textbox 1: Lessons from the UK on climate change mitigation policy planning including CCUS and CDR.

In the UK, industrial clusters have been funded to develop roadmaps for their transition to net zero: the Scottish Net Zero Roadmap,¹ Humber Industrial Cluster Plan,² South Wales Industrial Cluster,³ Net Zero North West Cluster Plan,⁴ Repowering the Black Country,⁵ and Net Zero Tees Valley Cluster Plan.⁶

In the UK the CCSA and Nuclear AMRC published a *CCUS Supply Chain Intervention Strategy* (Nuclear AMRC 2022). Key recommendations were:

- Develop a schedule of key components
- Launch a supplier development program
- Increase competitiveness with improved and new production processes
- Execute a CCUS-wide supply chain analysis program

To avoid conflicts and bottlenecks, this work should extend to all decarbonisation and low-carbon infrastructure.

The Scottish Government has established a Just Transition Commission,⁷ initially to advise Scottish Ministers on how to apply just transition principles,⁸ and subsequently to provide scrutiny and advice on Scottish Government-led sectoral just transition plans.

Stakeholders who responded to the survey additionally highlighted the need to understand the lifecycle cost of renewable energy.

3.1.4 Challenges relating to complexity of the CCUS value chain

The CCUS value chain – CO₂ capture, CO₂ transport and CO₂ storage or utilisation – is likely to involve different, and perhaps multiple, companies at each stage. This establishes cross-chain risk between the different stages of the CCS chain: for example, the CO₂ store developer

¹ For more details, see their website: <https://snzr.co.uk>

² For more details, see their website: <https://www.humberindustrialclusterplan.org/>

³ For more details, see their website: <https://www.swic.cymru/>

⁴ For more details, see their website: <https://netzeronw.co.uk>

⁵ For more details, see their website: <https://www.blackcountrylep.co.uk/our-strategy/place/repowering-the-black-country/>

⁶ For more details, see their website: <https://www.ukri.org/about-us/how-we-are-doing/research-outcomes-and-impact/innovate-uk/net-zero-tees-valley/>

⁷ For more details, see their website: <https://www.gov.scot/groups/just-transition-commission/>

⁸ Summarised as: Plan, invest and implement a transition to environmentally and socially sustainable jobs, sectors and economies, building on Scotland's economic and workforce strengths and potential; Create opportunities to develop resource efficient and sustainable economic approaches, which help address inequality and poverty; and Design and deliver low carbon investment and infrastructure, and make all possible efforts to create decent, fair and high value work, in a way which does not negatively affect the current workforce and overall economy.

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needs assurance that there will be a supply of CO₂ before they will invest, while a CO₂ emitter will need to be sure there is a destination for the CO₂ before investing in carbon capture.

This cross-chain risk may be compounded in a CCUS cluster, where there are even more organisations that need to reach an agreement. CCS has historically been conceived as part of large single-source-to-single-store projects (usually applied thermal power generation using fossil fuel), but as its potential for decarbonising many other industrial sources of CO₂ is increasingly well understood, the need for a multisectoral approach grows. This can include a shared CO₂ transport and storage system, which is available for all users, and means that support for infrastructure needs to be available at a time which lines up with support for capture at individual industries.

Additional complexity comes with projects that cross national or regional boundaries and jurisdictions especially in case of involvement in baseline-and-credit carbon market transactions where the ownership of credits is linked with questions of whether and how to financially address the economic cost of addressing leakage among partners along a complex CCUS value chain.

Clusters will need to consider:

- Availability and maturity of permanent and temporary CO₂ storage – including whether there are companies operating in the transport and storage sector.
- Availability of CO₂ transport infrastructure: this includes pipeline and non-pipeline transport. For shipping, attention will need to be paid to the availability and suitability of ships and port infrastructure. This is being explored by the EverLoNG project.⁹
- Readiness of value chain and operators – this links back to Interaction with other decarbonisation technologies, and issues of competition for resources, funding and skilled workers.

Beyond these headline considerations, other issues include:

- Allowing hydrogen or syngas into the gas grid to create a market for gases that have been produced using CCS
- Consistent approaches to CO₂ handling and CO₂ specifications across countries and different sectors' emission sources (e.g. requiring standards of CO₂ streams that are compatible between waste to energy, cement, biomass to energy, or DAC plants).
- Ability of ships to handle different types of gas

Survey respondents highlighted the complexity of the value chain and the importance of defining project roles and responsibilities and contractual arrangements. The uncertainty around the development of CCS and its place in the market also adds to the risks.

Some viewed timely development of transport and storage infrastructure as the key to unlocking the economics for CCUS clusters and providing industries with the opportunity to

⁹ For more details, see their website: <https://everlongccus.eu>

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use CCUS to decarbonise. This echoes the view of the UK's 2016 report *Lowest cost decarbonisation for the UK: the critical role of CCS* (Oxburgh, 2016).

3.1.5 Economic implications of complex marine and land-use planning processes

Marine and land-use planning can support or hinder deployment of CCS, depending on how they are done. The lack of experience with CO₂ storage sites and related infrastructure causes severe uncertainties, which affects economic viability and attractiveness. Planning policies are determined at the member state, region or more local level and determine what can be built where. Development planning can include a spatial determination of which developments are suitable for which locations, and/or policies to enable planners to decide applications for new developments or change or use / alterations to existing developments. Plans and planning policies can take many years to put in place and may not be designed to deal with new classes of development, such as CCS and hydrogen infrastructure. All these risks cause excessive barriers to entry and thus can have a deterrent effect on financing.

Issues that need to be addressed in spatial planning include how to deal with the potential for competing uses of the sea and seabed, such as for offshore wind, fishing, leisure, nature conservation etc. Competing use-cases for the same surfaces thus can raise the economic threshold for CCUS viability.

There may be the need for planning authorities to work together on cross-border infrastructure projects both when it comes to on- and offshore installations. Complex planning applications can take years and can threaten economic viability if this is not factored in at an early stage.

Planning is often associated with and has interrelationships with the environment, and health, and safety consenting and permitting. There is likely to be a need for training and capacity building for planners and regulators to know how to deal with new developments including CO₂ capture, and pipeline transport; and lack of capacity and knowledge can delay the process.

Excessive planning durations could lead to partners giving up early, thus challenging previously established business cases (as projections of cost and revenues change).

Textbox 2: Lessons from the UK on the possibilities for streamlined co-ordination of complementary infrastructure projects.

The UK's Energy Integration Project¹⁰ explores how different offshore energy systems (oil and gas, renewables, hydrogen and carbon capture and storage) could be co-ordinated across the UK Continental Shelf (UKCS) for environmental and efficiency gains, including identifying technical, regulatory, and economic hurdles.

In 2001, the Scottish Government and its partners carried out a regulatory test exercise to understand the many processes and permits required to develop a CCS project; based on this, Scottish Carbon Capture & Storage developed a CCS Regulatory Toolkit (Pegler and Imrie 2011). A review of the regulations around CCS in Scotland has since been updated but has not been published. These efforts can provide form lessons as they have taken an

¹⁰ For more details, see their website: <https://www.nstauthority.co.uk/the-move-to-net-zero/energy-integration/>

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integrative view guided by a vision of industrial development integrated with industrial decarbonization through CCUS.

3.1.6 Challenges relating to economic implications of ambiguities in long-term storage liability

The CO₂ Storage Directive requires that sometime after closure (to be determined by the competent authority, but at least 20 years) the responsibility for a CO₂ storage site can be transferred from the operator to the competent authority.

Differences in MS operationalization of the storage directive cause economic uncertainty, especially regarding cases of bankruptcies before transferal to national authorities.

Storage operators are required to provide financial security (or an equivalent, as determined by the competent authority) to ensure that all obligations under the directive can be met, including taking corrective measures to address and leakages and paying and surrendering EU ETS emissions trading allowances for any escaped CO₂. This has economic implications and any ambiguities (e.g. in permitting processes) can cause problems for economic viability.

Are governments prepared to take on the long-term liability for storage once stores have closed? Does it make a difference whether the CO₂ in them is from domestic or international sources?

3.2 MRV Methodologies and Accounting Issues

Monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV) is the process of tracking GHG flows at activity-level often to generate carbon credits under baseline-and-credit carbon markets or to track compliance with an emissions cap. GHG accounting in contrast generates a national-level account (in the GHG inventories Parties to the UNFCCC are required to maintain) of yearly emissions and removal flows taking place in the various economic sectors within a country's borders. Both are important components toward the credible tracking of mitigation results from CCU and CCS activities. And both are somewhat underdeveloped for CCU and CCS activities.

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Figure 1: Prominent issues regarding the consistent and credible tracking of results from various CCUS activities

3.2.1 Challenges relating to baseline-and-credit MRV methodologies

The monitoring and reporting regulation complements the ETS directive and regulates the monitoring and reporting obligations of entities subject to the ETS in detail with the purpose of ensuring that the incentives created by the trading system accurately mirror the emissions flows. It outlines the requirements regarding continued emissions measurement systems, quality assurance levels, compliance demonstration requirements, annual surveillance tests, cross-corroboration of measurements and emissions-calculations, measures in case of missing data and various analytical procedures data verification and control requirements (European Commission, 2018a). The verification and accreditation regulation regulates the verification of reports and the accreditation and supervision of third-party verifiers (European Commission, 2018b). As a well-tested system, the challenges of MRV under the ETS pertain solely to the lack of practice especially in regards to the newer forms of CCUS.

In contrast, the world of baseline-and-credit carbon markets lacks a harmonised framework for MRV methodologies. For CCS-related activities, the Clean Development Mechanisms provides project-level monitoring methodologies for CCS activities, which include definitions of variables that will affect the GHG reduction results of the project activity, measurement and calibration requirements, and procedures on Quality Assurance and Quality control (QA/QC). However, to date, the CDM has not approved CCS methodologies. For CDR, the existing MRV methodologies are limited in terms of geographical scope, activity types, or linkage to specific market mechanisms/regulatory frameworks. For instance, for carbon dioxide transport and geological storage, existing frameworks and protocols have different scopes and applicability (see Chapter 4). Fragmented efforts could promote the rise of low-quality removal credits and the double counting of carbon removal credits for mitigation purposes (Honegger *et al.* 2021). Currently, there is no international body that provides oversight for the MRV methodologies on CDR, which increases uncertainties for private buyers in voluntary carbon markets (Mercer

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and Burke 2023). When credits are generated and traded it is necessary to ensure that – when used to compensate for emissions – they represent the results of otherwise infeasible measures – i.e. that the additionally funded CCUS activities would not otherwise have been viable. In baseline-and-credit carbon markets this is to be ensured through additionality tests, yet many CCUS methodologies do not include a detailed additionality test (the Australian ERF methodology, however, includes a more robust approach to additionality testing (Poralla *et al.* 2022)).

Further, the authors highlight the importance of baseline setting, which is to define reference scenarios for greenhouse gas emissions, removals, and storage as well as to estimate leakage risks and uncertainty in the scenario. BECCS is considered to have a “natural” baseline in which CCS does not exist while the baseline for DACS is “no activity”. It suggests that in the future, baseline setting for national mitigation goals would incorporate removal options as a baseline, which would then demand large-scale carbon removal. However, there is a lack of baseline and monitoring methodologies that comprehensively consider the value chain for each carbon dioxide removal and carbon capture and storage (Poralla *et al.* 2022).

3.2.2 Challenges relating to accounting readiness

Accurate and transparent GHG inventories at national levels are crucial for tracking progress towards emissions reduction targets and informing climate policy decisions. A robust inventory system helps ensure that countries are held accountable for their emissions and can lead to increased trust and cooperation in international climate negotiations. It also helps to identify areas where emissions reduction efforts can be targeted most effectively.

Parties to the Paris Agreement are requested to keep track of their emissions, reductions, and removals, i.e., the emission balance, via national GHG inventories. National GHG inventories are the basis for emissions balances, which in turn are the basis of tracking progress and assessing achievement towards NDCs. Therefore, only removals that show up in the national GHG inventory lower the national emission levels in a way that contributes to the achievement of the host country’s NDC.

Parties are required to apply relevant IPCC guidance and best practices when doing their reporting. Some CCUS-based activities are already addressed by the latest guidance (IPCC 2019, IPCC 2006). The 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories offer guidance for estimating GHG emissions from CO₂ capture associated with combustion activities, particularly those relative to power plants, transport, injection, and storage systems (Poralla *et al.* 2022).

However, other especially more novel types such as direct air capture, are not yet reflected (Poralla *et al.* 2022). Hence, additional guidance by the IPCC on how to set up and reflect these novel types of removals in national GHG inventories is required.

3.2.3 Challenges relating to the accounting of storage and leakage

Whenever a new type of capture, transport or storage process is first piloted, staff tasked with updating the national GHG inventory may not be aware of or lack guidance for how to properly report these mitigation activities. For some types of CCUS value chains GHG inventory guidance may even be entirely missing.

The IPCC Special Report on Carbon Dioxide Capture and Storage notes that the guidelines on ‘the general framework and concepts’ are available on carbon capture and storage (IPCC

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2005, p. 431). In the reporting framework, the amount of CO₂ transported and stored could be reflected in the relevant sectors and categories or the new categories made for carbon transportation and storage. The first option treats CCS as a mitigation measure, reducing emissions by implementing CO₂ capture or using decarbonised fuels, while the second option reports the captured and stored amounts as CO₂ removals (sinks). In both cases, the additional energy required for injection processes in the storage sites would be also covered in the existing IPCC guidelines.

However, the detailed methodologies for monitoring and reporting physical leakage from storage sites are insufficient. The IPCC Special Report on Carbon dioxide Capture and Storage, notes that “long-term physical leakage of stored CO₂ is not covered by the existing framework for reporting of emissions in the IPCC Guidelines” (IPCC 2005, p.369). There are challenges in the accounting frameworks due to a lack of understanding about the rate of physical leakage from different storage options (i.e., possibilities for accidental releases over a very long time period (issues of permanence and liability). Further, additional energy use for CO₂ storage would need to be considered, while the liability and leakage can occur outside the existing accounting boundaries (see 0).

3.2.4 Challenges relating to accounting of CO₂ utilisation (CCU)

Carbon Capture and Utilisation (CCU) includes a variety of methods in which carbon dioxide is captured and used directly without being chemically altered (i.e., non-conversion) or in a transformed form for different purposes (i.e., conversion). CCU – in contrast to CCUS – does not store the CO₂ and as such can merely achieve a relative emissions reduction if – and only if – it displaces higher-emissions alternatives. Currently, CO₂ is mainly utilised in the production of fertilisers and for enhanced oil recovery (EOR) (IEA 2023a). Carbon dioxide can also be used as feedstock in the manufacturing of fuels, carbonates, polymers, and chemicals (e.g., plastics, ceramics, concrete) although the maturity levels of these technologies are generally lower.

The accounting of CO₂ utilisation as feedstock presents different challenges. First, accurately measuring and quantifying the net amount of CO₂ emissions in various industrial processes are challenging. For instance, energy use for CO₂ utilisation processes would need to be considered. Further, determining the environmental impact of CO₂ utilisation is crucial as CCU-derived products would have different lifespans (IEAGHG 2018). Life cycle assessment methodologies might not be comparable due to variations in relative basis for which environmental impacts are assessed (Müller *et al.* 2020). The functional unit definitions can vary depending on product properties and the number of applications (Table 3).

Table 3: Examples of CCU product applications and market segments

CCU class/ Properties	Substitutes				Non-substitutes
	Chemical products	Material products	Fuels	Energy storage systems	All
Basis for comparison	Mass	Material performance	Energy	Storage performance	Service or performance provided
Functional unit	e.g., mass, plant output	e.g., mass, plant output	e.g., energy, mass, plant output	e.g., energy, plant output	Compare the performance of new to existing solutions
Reference flow	e.g., 1 t methanol, 1.6 Mt/a plant output over 20 a	e.g., 1 t concrete, 50 kt/a plant output over 20 a	e.g., 1 MJ of H ₂ , 2.5 Mt/a diesel over 20 a	e.g., storing 1 MJ of electricity, 80 MWh battery	e.g., 1 t, 1 MJ, the output of conventional plant over 20 a

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Source: Zimmermann *et al.* (2020)

Lastly, different baseline or reference cases can create confusion when comparing the resulting products derived from CCU. While energy analysts typically use reference cases for comparative assessments of energy systems, lifecycle assessments are more commonly used among manufacturers and product analysts (IEAGHG 2018). These different approaches limit stakeholders' understanding of the net-climate advantages of CCU and CCU-derived products in comparison to the conventionally produced counterparts.

These challenges suggest that developing standardised accounting frameworks and methodologies specific to CO₂ utilisation will be essential to accurately assess its environmental implications.

3.2.5 MRV for the special case of CCUS associated with EOR

Carbon Capture Utilization and Storage (CCUS) is a particular form of CCU, whereby the carbon is stored durably in the product or the utilization results in durable storage. The latter is the case when captured carbon is utilised for EOR. The carbon that is injected underground overall ends up durably stored (though there is a heightened carbon content in the extracted fuels, which is extracted and reinjected under normal conditions). This is – of course – separate from the fact that the extracted oil or gas is likely to be combusted as fuel or later as plastic waste, thus resulting in emissions. Results based incentives need to be based on overall quantification of results including a full lifecycle perspective.

3.2.6 Challenges relating to the accounting of carbon dioxide removals

As already discussed in the previous challenge relating to accounting readiness, national greenhouse gas inventories serve for tracking developments in national emission balances. While the voluntary carbon removal market is growing as companies are willing to pay to offset their emissions, without a legal basis and standards for measuring or calculating CO₂ removals, there is little certainty or incentive for companies with existing biogenic CO₂ emissions to invest in capturing and storing them (Nehler and Fridahl 2022). Further, carbon dioxide removal technologies often encounter two common challenges, which are estimation of the net change in total emissions and permanence (Brander *et al.*, 2021). For instance, the deployment of BECCS may have indirect effects on the emissions by influencing land use through stronger demand for feedstock (Galik *et al.* 2023)

3.2.7 Challenges relating to the accounting of BECCS

While the EU climate objectives and accounting practices consider in principle engineered greenhouse gas removals to be counted in its inventory, it is unclear how to implement this for BECCS in national law (IEA 2022a). Existing IPCC guidance on greenhouse gas inventories is relevant for accounting of BECCS, but further improvements are needed to enhance transparency and comparability with other technologies. According to IPCC's 2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories, BECCS could be reported in several separate sections, 'geological storage', 'waste generation, composition, and management', and 'harvested wood products (HWP)'.

The HWP category was devised to monitor carbon flows, and particularly the accumulation within entire pools by assessing the net changes in carbon stored. The guidelines allow in principle for several accounting approaches which are incompatible amongst-one-another for

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relating to differences in system boundary definitions (Table 4). Under the Paris Agreement and its Enhanced Transparency Framework (ETF) Parties are supposed to use the 'production' approach.

Table 4: Overview of HWP accounting approaches

	HWP pool accounting	Risks	Not evaluated/tracked	Stock-change(s)
Production	Producing country	Emissions/removal are not accurately reflected. Obtaining explicit data on exported wood is challenging.	HWP pool imported. Where stock changes occur.	Pool-based
Simple decay				Flux-based
Atmospheric flow	Consuming country	Imported wood is counted as gain of carbon in the HWP pool.	HWP pool exported.	Flux-based
Stock-change(s)				Pool-based

Source: Michaelowa *et al.* (2023), Sato and Nojiri (2019)

Yet, it is challenging to accurately estimate the emission baseline when biomass is being exported. For instance, direct and indirect land-use changes from BECCS are not explicitly stated in IPCC guidelines (Galik *et al.* 2023). Under the territorial principle of IPCC Guidelines, "production" and "simple decay" approaches consider the HWP producing country as responsible for CO₂ emissions or removals. On the other hand, the "stock-change" and "atmospheric-flow" approaches burden or credit the consuming country (Table 4). However, all four accounting approaches face a challenge in accurately measuring the amount of carbon stored in the products as the carbon content is influenced by the type of product, the harvesting and processing techniques, and the length of time the product will be in use. Further, the question of who would be responsible for the re-emission of CO₂ from harvested wood products is unclear.

In current national GHG inventory reporting, net changes in carbon stocks and fluxes on land associated with biomass can be included. Additional guidance by the IPCC on how to best set up a national GHG inventory reflecting BECCS emission flows may be needed. Accounting for CO₂ removal through BECCS is key to scaling up the BECCS system (Torvanger 2019). Furthermore, there are no EU regulations that specify where BECCS should be accounted. More coordination between the EU and its member states and detailed instructions on how the EU climate objectives relate to domestic climate policies and national inventory infrastructure can help to align the processes between the EU and its member states; it is unclear whether the CRCF will help this (see section 3.2.12).

Another challenge for a large-scale ramp-up of BECCS activities worldwide is related to the actual source of biomass used for BECCS. Tools or taxonomy indicators, like those proposed in the EU taxonomy for sustainable activities (European Commission 2023c), are needed to transparently evaluate the sustainability of the used biomass because non-sustainably sourced biomass should not be used in large-scale BECCS operations.

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3.2.8 Challenges relating to the accounting of DACS

National greenhouse gas inventories serve for tracking developments in national emission balances, but Direct Air Capture does not clearly fit in with the current practices. While MRV methodologies in the IPCC Guidelines for National GHG inventories exist for emission reductions and BECCS to some extent, the guidelines for direct air capture are not readily available as it is a novel technology (IEA 2022b). Accordingly, there is some level of uncertainty regarding where, i.e., in which (sub-)sector of the inventory, to properly report the amount of CO₂ captured. The US offers some ideas on how to do this: the U.S. Department of Energy has published a report, *Best Practices for Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of Direct Air Capture with Storage (DACs)* in 2022, which provides specific best practices to harmonise methodologies for consistent assessments of CDR-related activities (US DoE 2022). While the report is based on the ISO 14040/14044 standards for conducting LCA (ISO 2022), the report notes that ISO standards are insufficient to specific guidance on DAC and storage. For instance, DOE presents seven different accounting methods for removed and avoided emissions on the net system of GHG emissions (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Direct Air Capture with Co-Product GHG Accounting Example: System

Source: US DoE (2022)

Pioneering countries including notably Iceland are also expected to soon start to capture significant volumes of CO₂ through DAC. As these pioneers start reporting in inventories, the IPCC taskforce on inventory guidance might adopt corresponding language in the IPCC Guidance reports that clarifies where DAC should be reported.

Removals have to date only been recognised in the land-use sector, and it may be confusing to report negative values for emissions within a sector sub-category. DAC may be most appropriately reported under the existing GHG inventory reporting (sub-) sector-categories,

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*Category 2.H.3. or Other.*¹¹ Additional IPCC guidance and instructions on how and where to best set up a national GHG inventory (sub-)sector-category reflecting DAC emission flows is needed.

3.2.9 Challenges relating to upstream responsibilities regarding leakages and other disturbances in joint hubs and clusters

In those cases where CO₂ capture is incentivized through national legislation, a CO₂ storage hub may pose some challenges as regarding the upstream responsibilities in case of leakage (or reversal) given that CO₂ from multiple sources is stored. In such a case it may not be clear how to attribute the leaked volumes to various regulatory- and market regimes under which upstream carbon capture entities operate.

EU regulations including the CCS and ETS directive regulate storage risks and responsibilities of leakage. Yet in private contracts stakeholders in a value chain may choose to shift responsibility and arrange for corresponding financial compensation amongst each other. There are thus three layers of legal arrangements that are to work hand in hand: Bilateral state agreements, national legislations (which transpose the EU directives), and private contracts between value-chain partners that operate within those regulatory landscapes to define specific responsibilities and modalities to ensure proper reporting and corrective action that ensures meeting upstream responsibilities.

3.2.10 Challenges relating to the operationalisation of the EU CCS Directive

The EU Directive 2009/31/EC on the geological storage of carbon dioxide and any amending Directives provide a legal framework for the safe geological storage of CO₂ within the European Economic Area (EEA), including risk assessment and liability determination (European Commission, 2023). As of the latest implementation report dated October 2023, the CCS Directive is considered to have been correctly applied in Member States.

The Directive sets out the legislative framework for the environmentally safe and permanent storage of carbon dioxide in the EU with the objective to mitigate any negative effects and risks to the environment and human health. Therefore, it includes detailed provisions on the selection of storage sites and exploration permits, storage permits and the operation and ultimate closure of storage sites. Geological storage sites shall have no significant risk of leakage and shall not pose any significant risks to the environment or health. Furthermore, any storage site shall be operated pursuant to a dedicated storage permit, with only one operator being allowed to use each storage site. Once a storage site is closed, a transfer of responsibility and liability takes place from the storage site operator to the respective national authority that is to be established by the MS, following a post-closure monitoring period of minimum 20 years and the demonstration of completely and permanently containment of the CO₂. According to Article 19 of the EU CCS Directive, the storage operators are expected to provide a financial contribution prior to transfer of responsibility and liability, covering “at least the anticipated cost of monitoring for the period of 30 years” (EU 2009).

¹¹ This suggestion has been discussed as a possible resolution, which appears fully in line with GHG inventory guidance, but – to the authors’ knowledge is not yet established common practice.

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The Directive also regulates third-party access to transportation networks and storage sites, asking MS to ensure that third parties can access these networks and storage sites. Such joint infrastructure around hubs, clusters and networks and subsequent issues around cross-border transport and dedicated MRV will likely become more relevant in the future.

The CCS Directive applies to CO₂ transport and operations, while EOR is not included. However, the Directive's preamble¹² provides that if EOR is combined with storage of CO₂, the provisions of the Directive apply accordingly. Our interpretation is that if a reservoir considered for EOR is selected and characterized according to the CCS Directive, and operated according to the directive's requirements, while quantifying and verifying the CO₂ ultimately being stored as part of the operations, CO₂ being injected and stored would generate ETS allowances for the emission source providing the CO₂, pursuant to the ETS Directive, c.f. MRR Article 49.

3.2.11 Challenges relating to the Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF)

The EU is developing a regulatory framework for certifying carbon removal, the so-called Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF). The objective of the CRCF is to scale up removal activities and to fight greenwashing by certifying removals that are generated in Europe and to develop adequate MRV methodologies for removals (European Commission 2023b). The Framework has been provisionally adopted in February 2024.

Certificates are expected to be generated in a process like activities of voluntary carbon market standards, but the EU Commission will decide on the eligible project types and MRV methodologies. Project types included span three very different categories of removal methods: 1) permanent removals involving geological storage, 2) removals involving durable storage in products, and 3) "carbon farming" removals. Categories 1 and 2 are relevant for CCU and CCS projects and it is imaginable that these two categories might eventually become eligible for creating revenues from the EU ETS.

Challenges to date can be identified regarding the scope, operation, and ultimate use of this framework, which might prevail for several years as the instrument matures. Examples of open questions and uncertainties that need to be resolved before becoming an issue include the relevance and eligibility of these credits for other EU climate policies, such as the Green Deal, EU ETS, ESR, LULUCF, Farm to Fork, and the circular economy. Moreover, it is unclear how "approved" credits under the CRCF will be differentiated from and maybe prioritised over other voluntary carbon market credits.

3.2.12 Challenges relating to voluntary carbon market standards

Although CCUS is increasingly seen as an important mitigation solution, in many cases it is still not economically viable. Hence, leveraging carbon markets to tap into their revenue streams and to scale up global mitigation efforts with CCUS is needed. While integration into existing compliance carbon markets might take more time, voluntary carbon markets can serve as a testbed and early-mover ecosystem, where required methodologies can be efficiently developed and robustly tested.

¹² [Recital](#) (20)

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For accessing (voluntary) carbon markets, robust carbon accounting and MRV methodologies for various types of CCUS activities are required. While some methodologies were developed for specific types of CCUS activities in the past, a comprehensive and high-quality set of methodologies applicable to all types of CCUS activities is missing. However, an industry consortium called the CCS+ Initiative is currently developing a methodological framework with robust requirements for MRV and additionality under Verra’s Verified Carbon Standard (VCS). The first set of methodologies, modules, and tools have been approved by an independent third-party validation and verification body (VVB) and Verra at the end of 2023. This will also include a tool to distinguish between emission reductions and removals. A parallel development is also taking place at the standard-setting body’s side. First, Verra is going to introduce two different labels for distinguishing reduction from removal projects at the registry level. Second, Verra has recently updated its VCS Program (Verra 2023a, 2023c) outlining requirements for geologic carbon storage activities and has also developed a so-called Non-Permanence Risk Tool for such activities, which ensures the integrity of projects while mitigating environmental, social, and safety risks (Verra 2023b).

In the realm of industrial standardization there are also industrial standardization processes ongoing both under the international standard ISO/TC 265 as well as – at European level – by the European Committee for Standardization.¹³

¹³ CEN/CENELEC, ‘a new CEN/T will develop standards for carbon capture, utilization and storage’
<https://www.cenelec.eu/news-and-events/news/2023/brief-news/2023-11-30-ccus/>

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4 Legal mapping

The legal mapping has consisted of a high-level screening of international and regional legal instruments applicable for the Baltic Sea Region and the Mediterranean Sea Region. This was done with the view of identifying what, if any, legal criteria exist for the storage of CO₂ under these instruments. The screening also considered national legal frameworks to determine whether storage is permitted, if this is onshore and/or offshore, full-scale, pilot-testing and/or R&D. The intention was to identify which countries allow for storage and the regulatory readiness to develop a CCUS value-chain, contributing towards the selection of case studies.

The most applicable international and regional legal instruments for the Baltic Sea Region and the Mediterranean Sea Region for CCUS are the 1996 London Protocol (London Protocol) to the 1972 Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Wastes and Other Matter (London Convention), the 1995 Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment and the Coastal Region of the Mediterranean (Barcelona Convention), the 1992 Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea Area (Helsinki Convention), the 1992 Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic (OSPAR Convention) and the EU CCS Directive. This section will identify obligations, criteria, issues and barriers under the aforementioned instruments and comment on the implications for the development of CCUS value-chains in the regions.

4.1 1996 London Protocol

The 1972 London Convention is one of the first international conventions seeking to protect the marine environment from human activities. It implements what is often referred to as the “black-and grey-list approach” to regulate dumping activities. The blacklist (Annex I) includes the wastes or other matter that one cannot dump, and the grey list (Annex II) lists the wastes or other matter that can be considered for dumping having acquired a prior special permit. Any other wastes or other matter not included on either of the two lists may be dumped with a general permit.

Recognising the need for a more preventative and precautionary approach to regulating dumping activities, the Contracting Parties conducted a review of the Convention. The review resulted in a new protocol: the 1996 London Protocol. While there are several similarities between the two instruments with respect to e.g., legal mechanisms, definitions and provisions, the Protocol is more restrictive and precautionary and introduces, *inter alia*, general obligations such as the polluter-pays principle and the precautionary approach. Most important for CCS operations, however, was the departure from the black-and grey-list approach in favour of the “reverse-list approach”.

Under the London Protocol, the reverse-list approach implies that there is a general ban on all dumping activities. Only the wastes and other matter listed as an exception to this ban in Annex 1 (i.e., the reverse list) may be considered for dumping having first acquired a permit. The implications are that all other wastes or other matter not listed in Annex 1 cannot be dumped. The Protocol defines dumping in Article 1(4)(1) and includes, *inter alia*, “any storage of wastes or other matter in the seabed and the subsoil thereof from vessels, aircraft, platforms

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or other man-made structures at sea.”¹⁴ Storage of CO₂ therefore falls within the definition of dumping. It should be noted that the Protocol only applies to offshore storage, not onshore.

Initially, CO₂ was not listed as an exception in Annex 1 and was therefore prohibited to store. Recognising the problem this caused for CCS operations, CO₂ was added to the list through an amendment in 2006. The amendment simultaneously set out criteria for the storage of CO₂ to occur. This provided the legal basis in international environmental law to regulate the storage of CO₂ in sub seabed geological formations. In addition to this, the permit procedures must comply with the Annex 2 requirements. This includes, *inter alia*, site selection and characterisation, waste assessment, monitoring and reporting, and permit conditions.

4.1.1 Article 6: Export Prohibition

Article 6 prohibits the export of wastes and other matter across borders for the purpose of dumping or incineration at sea. The intention with the prohibition is to prevent Contracting Parties from evading their obligations under the Protocol by sending their wastes and other matter to other countries not bound by the London Protocol for dumping, all the while, on the face of it, being in compliance. Article 6 was problematic for the development of storage facilities intended to receive quantities of CO₂ from other countries – which may be necessary for the large-scale deployment of CCS. To mitigate this, a new amendment to the Protocol was proposed in 2009. The amendment adds a second paragraph to Article 6 exempting CO₂ exported for offshore storage from the prohibition.

The new Article 6.2 mandates the conclusion of an arrangement or agreement between the countries involved, which shall confirm and allocate permitting responsibilities between the parties consistent with the provisions of the Protocol and applicable international law.

In the case where CO₂ is exported from a Contracting Party to a non-Contracting Party, the arrangement or agreement must contain provisions that, at a minimum, are equivalent to those contained in the Protocol. This includes those relating to the issuance of permits and permit conditions. This is done to make sure that the obligations under the Protocol are always met. To meet these requirements, the Contracting Party must undertake a due diligence of the non-Contracting Parties national framework to ensure itself that the CO₂ will be stored according to the provisions of the Protocol. The burden of ensuring compliance rests with the Contracting Party as treaty obligations cannot be imposed on non-Contracting Parties without its consent (1969 Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties, Article 34). Indeed, the resolution giving effect to the 2009 amendment makes clear that “accountability for compliance with the provisions of the Protocol will rest with the Contracting Party in the case of export to non-Contracting Parties” (Resolution LP.3(4) on the amendment to article 6 of the London Protocol, 2009).

The new paragraph 2 is relatively short and gives Contracting Parties some discretion vis-à-vis the preferred shape, content, and legal nature of the arrangement or agreement. The Contracting Parties issued a guidance document on the interpretation of Article 6.2 intended to assist the Contracting Parties when drafting the arrangement or agreement (Guidance on the implementation of Article 6.2 on the export of CO₂ streams for disposal in sub-seabed

¹⁴ London Protocol, art. 1(4)(1)(3).

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geological formations for the purpose of sequestration, LC 35/15, Annex 6). While the document is useful in adding flesh to the bones of Article 6.2, actual state practice will be the most useful tool in answering the remaining questions – as the guidance document acknowledges. At the time of writing,¹⁵ the only examples of agreements and arrangements concluded under Article 6.2 have been between European countries. These will be introduced in 4.1.2 below.

The Protocol contains procedures and requirements for the entry into force of amendments made to the Protocol and its annexes (London Protocol, Articles 21-22). The Protocol requires that 2/3 of the Contracting Parties have formally accepted the amendment for it to enter into force, a majority which has not yet been reached for the 2009 amendment. In 2019, Norway and the Netherlands suggested the interim solution of provisional application which became effective through the 2019 Resolution. As a result, Contracting Parties can provisionally apply the 2009 amendment and export CO₂ across borders for offshore storage, provided they have deposited a declaration of provisional application to the IMO and that the requirements in Article 6.2 have been met. As such, there are no barriers left under the Protocol to the cross-border transportation and offshore storage of CO₂.

4.1.2 Arrangement and agreements concluded under Article 6.2

The world's first arrangement concluded under Article 6.2 was between Denmark and Belgium for Project Greensand in September 2022. The first injection was 08 March 2023, marking the world's first cross-border offshore CO₂ storage. The arrangement is a Memorandum of Understanding (DK-BE MoU) and is relatively short containing only five Sections: 1) Scope, 2) Allocation of permits, 3) Arrangements of the Participants, 4) Amendment procedures and mutual understanding, and 5) Final Provisions.

Section 2 makes clear that “the Participants recognize that all necessary permit responsibilities will be allocated to the relevant authorities of each Participant’s country in accordance with the London Protocol” and provides a non-exhaustive list of relevant permitting authorities. This appears to satisfy the Article 6.2 requirement of confirmation and allocation of permitting responsibilities.

In June 2023, Belgium and the Netherlands also concluded a MoU under Article 6.2 (BE-NL MoU). While there are some small differences between the BE-NL and DK-BE MoUs,¹⁶ the MoUs are overall highly similar with respect to structure, language and content. The similarities between the MoUs could suggest that a ‘standardised’ London Protocol MoU format for cross-border transportation of CO₂ under Article 6.2 has been, or is being, developed in Europe. The implication of having a MoU format or template is that future cross-border projects that require an arrangement under the London Protocol could be streamlined. The Contracting Parties that take this format into use could save time drafting a completely new arrangement and adjust the format as needed (Ombudstvedt *et al.* 2023). However, whether MoUs are the preferred approach given the complexity of issues such as liabilities,

¹⁵ April 2024

¹⁶ Section 5 of the DK-BE MoU provides for termination by either party giving 12 month’s written notice, the BE-NL Section 5 provides for 3 months prior written notice.

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MRV and public acceptance, remains to be seen. Having legally binding and more detailed agreements may have clear benefits.

Recently, France and Denmark concluded a MoU for the purpose of Article 6.2 in March 2024 (FR-DK MoU). This MoU is also very similar to the BE-NL and DK-BE MoUs, which supports the argument made above that a London Protocol MoU format or template is being, or has been, developed – at least in Europe.

Norway has been negotiating cross-border collaborations with several countries. In the CCS Directive country report from 2023, the Ministry of Petroleum and Energy (now Ministry of Energy) noted that the export of CO₂ to Norway would be subject to a bilateral agreement, and that the government had approved a model agreement which would form the basis of their negotiations with other countries. They observed that:

[t]hese agreements will address the transfer of responsibility for any leakage or other incidents between Norway and the exporting country along the value chain for the CO₂ to be exported, and to which country obligations to report and monitor CO₂ leakages apply in accordance with EU legislation and international obligations. In addition, the bilateral agreement will form the basis for commercial agreements between Norwegian companies licenced under the Storage Regulation and companies from the exporting country.

The Ministry then confirmed that Norway was in final stages of negotiating a bilateral agreement with Sweden, and that talks were ongoing with Denmark and Belgium, among others. However, in April 2024, Norway concluded MoUs with Sweden, Belgium, the Netherlands and Denmark. As such, it appears that they have departed from the preferred default of using agreements. Whether the Norwegian government intends to use MoUs in each case going forward, or return to an agreement, remains to be seen. An agreement under the London Protocol would be the first of its kind. The MoU between the Netherlands and Norway is similar to the MoUs concluded between DK-BE, BE-NL and FR-DK, but with some important new additions. A new section (3) on Reporting of CO₂ in National Greenhouse Gas Inventories was included delivering on the statement made in the country report. The MoU also sets out a more detailed preamble, accounting for relevant international and regional conventions and instruments to which the parties are bound. Moreover, this is the only MoU that refers to London Protocol Annex 2 and observes that the participants will notify the IMO of the MoU. This is the only MoU by Norway that has been published at the time of writing.

It is important to highlight that all the examples of Article 6.2 arrangements as discussed above are between Contracting Parties to the London Protocol. While there are several ongoing discussions between both Contracting Parties and non-Contracting Parties on cross-border CCS projects, we have yet to see an Article 6.2 arrangement or agreement between a Contracting Party exporting to a non-Contracting Party. In this event, as mentioned, the new Article 6.2 puts an obligation on the Contracting Parties to make sure that the CO₂ exported is always stored according to the provisions of the Protocol. An arrangement or agreement between a Contracting Party and non-Contracting Party would be the first of its kind and demonstrate how Contracting Parties can meet their due-diligence obligation under the Protocol.

Of the Baltic Sea Region countries included in ZEN, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Germany, and Sweden are Contracting Parties to the London Protocol. Denmark, Estonia, Finland, and Sweden have accepted the 2009 amendment, and Sweden and Denmark have further

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deposited declarations of provisional application and also concluded arrangements. Latvia, Lithuania, and Poland are not parties to the London Protocol. In the Mediterranean Sea Region, France, Italy and Spain are parties to the London Protocol, but none have accepted the 2009 amendment or submitted a declaration of provisional application (note that this is underway for Italy and France). Türkiye and Greece are not Contracting Parties. It is clear from the sections above that membership to the Protocol can impact cross-border CCUS value chains by providing criteria for such cross-border collaboration to occur. It should be noted again that the London Protocol only applies to offshore storage and has no bearing on onshore storage. As such, the Protocol will be important when assessing the case studies where the storage site is offshore. The following sections will introduce the applicable regional sea conventions and comment on the implications for the Contracting Parties.

4.2 North-East Atlantic – OSPAR Convention

Merging and updating two pre-existing Conventions,¹⁷ the OSPAR Convention seeks to protect the marine environment in the North-East Atlantic. The Convention was open for signature at the Ministerial Meeting of the Oslo and Paris Commissions in 1992 and entered into force in 1998. The Convention's Annexes and Appendices form an integral part of the Convention, and expand on the general obligations contained in the articles.

Initially, Annex II (prevention and elimination of pollution by dumping or incineration) and Annex III (elimination of pollution from offshore sources) prohibited storage of CO₂ and were subsequently amended in 2007 to allow for such activities. Annex II introduces a general ban on dumping activities with the exception of the waste or other matter explicitly listed in the Annex which in each case requires a permit. As CO₂ was not included on the list of exceptions (having implemented a reverse-list approach), it was prohibited to store. This is because storage falls within the definition of dumping. As such, the Annex was amended by adding CO₂ to the list of wastes or other matter that may be considered for dumping, simultaneously setting out criteria for such storage to occur. These criteria are the same as the London Protocol but includes one additional criterion which underlines that the CO₂ is to be retained in the formations permanently and will not lead to significant adverse consequences for the marine environment, human health, and other legitimate uses of the maritime area (OSPAR, Annex II, Article 3(2)(f)(iv)).

Another amendment was made to Annex III Article 3 which otherwise bans any dumping of wastes or other matter from offshore installations, except for discharges or emissions from offshore sources. A new paragraph 3 was introduced which exempts storage of CO₂ from this ban. In addition to these amendments, the OSPAR Commission adopted Decision 2007/02 to ensure the safe storage of CO₂ in geological formations and guidelines for risk assessment and management of storage of CO₂ streams in geological formations (OSPAR Guidelines).¹⁸ The OSPAR Commission also adopted Decision 2007/01 to prohibit storage in the water column or on the seabed. Following these amendments, the OSPAR Convention is the only

¹⁷ 1972 Convention for the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping from Ships and Aircrafts and the 1974 Convention for the Prevention of Marine Pollution from Land-Based Sources.

¹⁸ OSPAR Guidelines for Risk Assessment and Management of Storage of CO₂ Streams in Geological Formations (reference number: 2007-12).

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regional sea convention in Europe with a dedicated framework that permits and regulates offshore storage CO₂.

The OSPAR Contracting Parties included in ZEN are Denmark, Sweden, Norway, Spain, France, Germany, and Finland (and the EU).

4.3 Baltic Sea – Helsinki Convention

The Helsinki Convention seeks to protect the marine environment of the Baltic Sea Area from all sources of pollution. It was initially adopted in 1974 with entry into force in 1980 but was later amended in 1992 following geopolitical developments and emerging environmental challenges in the region. The amended Convention entered into force in 2000. The Helsinki Convention has seven Annexes which contain more detailed procedures, measures and regulations linked to the objectives, principles and obligations set out in the Convention.

Article 11 on the prevention of dumping prohibits dumping of all wastes and other matter in the Convention area, except for dredged material. Dumping of dredged material requires in each case a prior special permit in accordance with the provisions of Annex V of the Protocol. This implies that storage of CO₂ is prohibited in the Baltic Sea Area. Any storage must therefore, as of today, be onshore in the Baltic region. Onshore, there are no international conventions that directly regulate or ban storage of CO₂; rather, this is regulated under the CCS Directive which observes that it is the individual Member State's prerogative to decide whether to allow storage of CO₂ or not on their territory (CCS Directive, Article 4). There are several countries in the Baltic region where onshore storage is either restricted (i.e., allowing only for R&D) or prohibited altogether.

For Sweden, being a party to both the OSPAR and Helsinki Convention, the implication is that the part of the Swedish continental shelf that is included in the geographical scope of the Helsinki Convention (the eastern continental shelf) is off limits for storage, while the western continental shelf bordering Norway and Denmark is permissible to use for this purpose, as it falls outside the scope of the Helsinki Convention and is under the OSPAR regime. The same applies for Denmark, where parts of the eastern continental shelf extend into the Baltic Sea and is therefore regulated under the Helsinki Convention. Denmark's western, northern and parts of the eastern continental shelf falls within the OSPAR Convention where storage is permitted. The Commission to the Helsinki Convention has made clear that the Convention is amended whenever deemed necessary, such as to follow the developments in international environmental and maritime laws. This means that while storage is prohibited today, it may change in the future to follow the developments occurring under e.g., the London Protocol and the OSPAR Convention.

The Contracting Parties to the Helsinki Convention that are included in ZEN are Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland and Sweden (and the EU).

4.4 Mediterranean Sea – Barcelona Convention

The Convention for the Protection of the Mediterranean Sea Against Pollution (Barcelona Convention 1976) was adopted in 1976. It was amended and renamed in 1995 to take into account new international development and best practices and include coasts in its scope. The new convention, titled Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment, and the

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Coastal Region of the Mediterranean (Barcelona Convention) entered into force in 2004 and has a total of seven protocols.

The two Dumping Protocols are particularly relevant for offshore CCS activities. Similar to the Convention itself, the first Dumping Protocol was adopted in 1976, but was amended in 1995. The 1976 Protocol is similar to the London Convention and regulates dumping activities through the black and grey-list approach. Annex I of the 1976 Protocol lists the waste and other matter that cannot be dumped (black list) and Annex II lists the wastes and other matter may be considered for dumping having acquired a prior special permit (grey list). All other wastes or other matter may be dumped pursuant to a general permit (Article 6). General and special permits shall be issued in line with Annex III requirements. CO₂ is not included in Annex I, but could potentially fall under Annex II, namely section 4. Thus, CO₂ may be stored either with a general or special permit. It should be noted that the definition of dumping includes “any deliberate disposal at sea of wastes or other matter from ships or aircraft”.

A question therefore arises whether “at sea” should be interpreted to include the sub-seabed. If sub-seabed is interpreted to be outside the scope of the Protocol, the Protocol may not apply to storage activities. However, Article 4.1 of Barcelona Convention provides that the parties shall take

all appropriate measures in accordance with the provisions of this Convention and those Protocols in force to which they are party to prevent, abate, combat and to the fullest possible extent eliminate pollution of the Mediterranean Sea Area and to protect and enhance the marine environment in that Area so as to contribute towards its sustainable development.

Also, the definition of “pollution” means “the introduction by man, directly or indirectly, of substances or energy into the **marine environment**” (Article 2(a); our emphasis). As one would have to access the sub-seabed through the water column and thus introduce the marine environment to energy by e.g., drilling an injection well, and that one may introduce the marine environment to substances if there is a leak at the injection site or from the storage site, and the parties have accepted to “prevent, abate, combat and to the fullest possible extent eliminate pollution”, it would be natural to interpret the scope to include also the sub-seabed in the actual scope of the Convention. However, at the time of drafting, technologies to store CO₂ under the seabed were not readily available and probably not part of the vocabulary. Even offshore oil and gas exploration was early phases.¹⁹ This may explain why the sub-seabed is not mentioned. However, the Convention emphasises the need “to pursue the protection of the marine environment and the natural resources of the Mediterranean Sea Area as an integral part of the development process, meeting the needs of present and future generations in an equitable manner”²⁰, which may be interpreted to support a dynamic approach. Thus, not having imagined CCS with CO₂ storage in the sub-seabed should not be taken as an argument to exclude it from the scope. Later protocols to the Conventions support

¹⁹ Craig J., Francesco G., MacAulay F., Sorkhabi R., ‘the history of the European oil and gas industry (1600s-2000)’ (Lyell collection) <https://www.lyellcollection.org/doi/full/10.1144/SP465.23>

²⁰ Barcelona Convention, Article 4.2

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this interpretation. The 1995 Dumping Protocol defines dumping to include among other things “any deliberate disposal or storage and burial of wastes or other matter on the seabed or in the marine subsoil”²¹ and the Protocol for the Protection of the Mediterranean Sea Against Pollution from Exploration and Exploitation of the Continental Shelf and the Seabed and its Subsoil (Offshore Protocol) have clarified the scope to also include the seabed and the subsoil, in line with technology development and the need of present and future generations. Thus, in our analysis, the inclusion of the seabed, subsoil and subsea geological formations is the baseline, also for the 1976 protocol, which is only referring to the “sea”.²²

The amended 1995 Protocol is more similar to the London Protocol and is therefore more restrictive and precautionary. As with the London Protocol, the 1995 Dumping Protocol departs from its predecessor’s black-and grey-list approach in favour of the reverse list. Only the waste or other matter listed in Article 4(2) may be considered for dumping, acting as exceptions to the general ban introduced in Article 4(1). Here, one encounters the same issue as the London Protocol²³, OSPAR Convention²⁴ and Helsinki Convention did before it – CO₂ is not listed as an exception and can therefore not be stored as the definition of dumping includes storage activities.

The 1995 Protocol has, however, not entered into force. The implications are that the 1976 Protocol still applies and one may be able to store CO₂ with a general or special permit. If the 1995 Protocol enters into force unamended, storage CO₂ would be prohibited. It is likely that CO₂ would have to be added to the list of exceptions in Article 4 to allow for this activity, as was the case with the OSPAR Convention and London Protocol before it.

A Draft Framework for Risk Assessment and Management of Storage of CO₂ Streams in Geological Formations in the Mediterranean Basin was prepared in 2013 (UNEP(DEPI)/MED WG.387/Inf.14, 29 July 2013, Draft Framework for Risk Assessment and Management of Storage of CO₂ Streams in Geological Formations). The Framework provides generic guidance to the Contracting Parties to the Barcelona Convention and provides that storage should not be permitted by a Contracting Party without authorisation or regulation by their competent authorities. Any authorisation or regulation shall be in accordance with the abovementioned Framework, as updated from time to time.

The Contracting Parties to the Convention that are included in ZEN are France, Spain, Italy, Greece, and Türkiye (and the EU).

4.5 CCU

The European Commission is currently developing a regulatory framework relevant for CCU, in terms of facilitating for CO₂ being used in feedstock or resource for products such as polymers, building materials, chemicals and synthetic fuels, and services.²⁵ Some parts are

²¹ 1995 Dumping Protocol to the Barcelona Convention, art. 3(3)c.

²² 1976 Dumping Protocol, art. 3

²³ Pre 2006 amendment.

²⁴ Pre 2007 amendments.

²⁵ European Commission, ‘Why do we need carbon capture, use and storage?’ [Overview - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

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more advanced (e.g. CCU fuels, mineralisation), others are still in the making (e.g. CCU chemicals). There is no one-stop instrument for CCU, but provisions and incentives may be found in several places. Relevant instruments for CCU include, *inter alia*, the Renewable Energy Directive, the ETS and Monitoring and Reporting Regulations, the proposed Carbon Removal Certification Framework, and the newly introduced ReFuelEU Aviation and Fuel EU Maritime, which collectively provide both incentives and a push for Member States to implement both targets and frameworks to take CCU technologies into use to reduce emissions and replace fossil fuels with renewable equivalents. Most of these instruments have been revised or introduced as part of the Fit-for-55 package, which sets proposals to revise and update EU legislation and put in place new initiatives to reach the goal of reducing net GHG emissions in the EU by at least 55% by 2030, and climate neutrality by 2050. Others (e.g. CRCF) are complementary to the actions taken under the Fit-for-55 package. CCU has further been identified and included as one of three key pathways in the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy, where it was recognised that “by replacing fossil-based feedstocks, CCU can contribute to emission reduction, energy security and autonomy of the EU” (Industrial Carbon Management Strategy, 4.4). The aforementioned instruments will be considered in this section, introducing pieces of the puzzle.

4.5.1 The Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF)’s relevance for CCU

The purpose of the CRCF is to offer methodologies and a process for certifying carbon removals in the EU to scale up such activities and having criteria to define high quality carbon removals and the process to monitor, report and verify their authenticity.

On November 21, 2023, the European Parliament voted to strengthen the draft CRCF regulation, also introducing obligations for the European Commission to report on the “need for potential EU targets for permanent carbon removals, such as bioenergy with CCS (BECCS) and direct air capture (DAC), along with land-based sequestration”.

The new draft proposes a renaming of the CRCF, to Carbon Farming, Carbon Storage in Products, and Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CFCPCRCF), recognising that the proposal included activities that were not unambiguously fitting the ‘removal’ terminology.

The legislation defines as permanent removals DACCS and BECCS, but also one specific CCU pathway; that is, mineralisation. This is considered as a permanent removal under the legislation when using DAC and biogenic CO₂ and the CO₂ is stored permanently

The deployment of Carbon Storage in Products is highlighted as one of several activities to contribute to emissions reductions or removals whereby its article 2, paragraph 1, point 1 defines carbon removal involving carbon storage in products as “a carbon removal activity that stores atmospheric and biogenic carbon in long-lasting products or materials.” The legislation indicates that a future delegated act will provide further definitions, criteria and thresholds, for how CO₂ stored in long lasting products can be considered as removals.

Article 6 in the draft contain a provision securing the operators to demonstrate the “long-term requirement”, and the proposed Article 6, paragraph 2a, stipulate that the monitoring period shall “cover the entire lifetime of the product until and including the end of the life of the product”.

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The draft also contains provisions on what is required to consider that such an activity shall be seen to “provide a net carbon storage in products benefit”, reference Article 4, paragraph 2a in the draft, and standardised baselines may be used, Article 4, paragraph 5.

The draft also provides regulation on liabilities, certification methodologies, public registries, standardisation, and best practices. A key term is also “reversals”. The latter term defined as voluntary or involuntary release of carbon back into the atmosphere in Article 2, paragraph 1, that also refer to the word “leakage” in the CCS Directive.

4.5.2 The Renewable Energy Directive’s Relevance for CCU

The Renewable Energy Directive (RED) sets an overall renewable energy target in the EU’s total energy consumption. Since the introduction of the RED in 2009 (2009/28/EC), the share of renewable energy sources in the EU’s energy consumption has increased from 12.5% in 2010 to 23% in 2022. The RED was revised in 2018 and most recently again in 2023. The RED from 2018 (REDII) introduced a target for the EU of 32% by 2023, with a clause for a possible upwards revision by 2023.²⁶ The recast Directive from 2023 (REDIII) sets a new binding target of 42.5% for the share of energy from renewable sources in the EU’s gross final consumption²⁷ of energy in 2030 but with an aspirational additional 2,5% target, making for a total of 45%. Member States shall set national contributions to collectively meet the binding target as part of their integrated national energy and climate plans in accordance with of Regulation 2018/1999 on the governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action (REDIII, article 3(2)). The target was set in recognition of the need to speed up the EU’s clean energy transition, meeting the European Green Deal and the REPowerEU objectives.

REDIII encourages the deployment of CCU-based fuels to replace fossil fuels in key sectors. (Industrial Carbon Management Strategy, 4.4). Indeed, in addition to introducing targets for the use of energy from renewable sources in the relevant sectors, the Directive also introduces targets for, *inter alia*, renewable fuels of non-biological origin (RFNBO). The Directive also defines recycled carbon fuels (RCFs) which can contribute to some of the targets set at EU level.

For example, Article 25 first provides that Member States shall set an obligation on fuel suppliers to ensure that the amount of renewable fuels and renewable electricity supplied to the transport sector leads to a share of renewable energy in the transport sector of at least 29% by 2030, or a GHG intensity reduction of at least 14,5% by 2030 (Article 25(1)(a)). Member States may to consider recycled carbon fuels (RCF) for the calculation of these targets (Article 25(3)). Article 25 then introduces a target for the combined share of advanced biofuel and biogas and RFNBO in the energy supplied to the transport sector of 1% in 2025 and 5,5% in 2030, of which a share of at least 1 percentage point is from RFNBOs.²⁸

²⁶ European Commission, ‘Renewable Energy Directive’ https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/renewable-energy/renewable-energy-directive-targets-and-rules/renewable-energy-directive_en

²⁷ The gross final consumption of energy from renewable sources in each Member State shall be calculated as the sum of: (a) gross final consumption of electricity from renewable sources; (b) gross final consumption of energy from renewable sources in the heating and cooling sector; and (c) final consumption of energy from renewable sources in the transport sector (art. 7 REDIII).

²⁸ Member States with maritime ports should also endeavour to ensure that the share of RFNBOs in the total amount of energy supplied to the maritime transport sector is at least 1,2% from 2030.

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Calculations rules are provided in Article 27, which also refers to delegated acts. Article 29a provides GHG emissions savings criteria for RFNBO and RCF, making clear that the RFNBO and RCF shall only be counted if the GHG savings from the use of those fuels are at least 70% compared to their fossil equivalent. Two delegated acts have been adopted: 1) the Delegated Act on a methodology for RFNBO, which defines what constitutes RFNBO. It introduces the additionality requirement and the criteria on temporal and geographic correlation, which seeks to ensure that these fuels can only be produced from additional renewable electricity generated at the same time and in the same areas as their own production. The second delegated act sets the methodology to calculate GHG emissions from RFNBOs and RCF.

Another example may be found in Article 22(a) which contains provisions to increase the share of renewable sources for industry, requiring that at least 42% of the hydrogen used for final energy and non-energy purposes in industry by 2030 and 60% by 2035 shall stem from RFNBOs (Article 22a(a) (1)). Under certain circumstances, this target may be reduced (see Article 22b).

The energy from RFNBO is to be counted in the sector where it is consumed. That said, Member States may agree, by virtue of a specific cooperation agreement, to count all or part of the RFNBO consumed in one Member State towards the share of gross final consumption of energy from renewable sources in the Member State where those fuels are produced (Article 7(1) fourth subparagraph). The Member States must notify the Commission of such agreements to make sure that the RFNBOs are not counted in both Member States. Importantly, Member States shall ensure that any national rules concerning the authorisation, certification and licensing procedures that are applied to, *inter alia*, RFNBO are proportionate and necessary and contribute to the implementation of the energy efficiency principle (Article 15). Article 15 further provides that Member States are to take steps to ensure that administrative procedures are streamlined and expedited, and predictable timeframes are established.

Thus, REDIII provides specific targets and incentives for CCU fuels, as well as provisions to simplify and speed up the permitting procedures, contributing towards an increase in production, demand, and use of such fuels.

4.5.3 Relevance of the EU ETS for CCU

The ETS cap and trade system is not traditionally a regime focusing on CCU, and the main incentives for CCU deployment are not contained in the ETS. However, there are provisions in there providing incentives for CCU technologies as well, ensuring incentives for deployment. As an example, to the technologies accounted for in the REDIII, the ETS Directive Article 14 provides for adoption of implementing acts for monitoring and reporting, in which it shall be specified how to account for emissions from RFNBO, as well as RCF, “ensuring that such emissions are accounted for, and that double counting is avoided”.

In MRR Article 49, which is significant for CCS, there is also a connection between the ETS regime and CCU, in which the provision provides for “[subtraction] from the emissions of the installation any amount of CO₂ originating from fossil carbon in activities covered by Annex I to Directive 2003/87/EC that is not emitted from the installation” which is “transferred out of the installation and used to produce precipitated calcium carbonate, in which the used CO₂ is chemically bound.” Thus, an emission source may subtract the CO₂ volumes which are

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captured, transported, and used for calcium carbonate, providing the emission source with the option to both deliver or sell the CO₂ for CCU processes as well as sell potential allowances on the ETS market. The recent ETS reform also provided updates to support CCU technologies with the potential to contribute “substantially” to climate change mitigation (Article 10(a)8) through e.g., access to the Innovation Fund. Also, allowances for emissions considered to have been captured, utilised and “permanently chemically bound in a product” do not need to be surrendered (Article 12(3b)). To qualify the permanency criterion, it is explained that the CO₂ cannot enter the atmosphere again “under normal use” of the product. However, more details are to be provided through a future delegated act. This amendment thus provides more options for emitters to capture and use CO₂. The EU carbon removal certification framework, accounted for in 4.5.1 above, will seemingly provide an option of certifying carbon removals generated by storing CO₂ in products in a manner that prevents the carbon to be re-emitted to the atmosphere (Industrial Carbon Management Strategy, 4.4). The rules are expected to be the same for mineralisation in ETS for fossil carbon, and for biogenic/DAC CO₂ under the CRCF.

Another important element of the ETS reform is the free allocation of a maximum of 20 million allowances from 2024 to 2030 to aircraft operators to cover the remaining cost-difference for the deployment of RFNBO and sustainable alternative fuels (Industrial Carbon Management Strategy 4.4). This further strengthens the position for RFNBOs. As may be seen in 4.5.4 below, the ReFuelEU aviation rules also require, from 2030, RFNBO to also cover synthetic fuels produced with renewable energy through CCU. Similarly, as accounted for in 4.5.5 below, the FuelEU Maritime Regulation puts in place a special incentive regime to support the uptake of RNFBOs. An important element of EU ETS recognising such CCU fuels will thus be to avoid double counting the embodied carbon emissions.

Further, the 2023 amendment to the ETS Directive provided for an obligation for the EU Commission by July 2026 to assess whether all the emissions covered by the Directive have been effectively accounted for as well as to consider if double accounting has been avoided. A part of this assessment would be to consider the accounting related to CCU for products, and whether the CO₂ potentially released from non-permanent CCU products and fuels should be accounted at the point of emission to the atmosphere (‘downstream accounting’) or when the CO₂ is initially captured (‘upstream accounting’).

4.5.4 The relevance of the ReFuel EU Aviation regulation for CCU

In 2023, the Council adopted a new regulation to decarbonise the aviation sector as part of the Fit for 55 package. The ReFuel EU Aviation Regulation aims to ensure a level playing field across the EU air transport market while gradually increasing the shares of sustainable air fuels (SAF), providing rules on the uptake and supply of SAF.

As summarised by the Council of the EU, the regulation provides:

- An obligation for aviation fuel suppliers to ensure that all fuel made available to aircraft operators at EU airports contains a minimum share of SAF from 2025 and, from 2030, a minimum share of synthetic fuels, with both shares increasing progressively until 2050. Fuel suppliers must incorporate 2% SAF in 2025, 6% in 2030 and 70% in 2050. From 2030, 1,2% of fuels must also be synthetic fuels, rising to 35% in 2050.
- The scope of eligible SAF and synthetic aviation fuels includes certified biofuels, RFBNO and recycled carbon aviation fuels complying with the RED sustainability and

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emissions saving criteria, up to a maximum of 70% with the exception of biofuels from food and feed crops, as well as low carbon aviation fuels (including low-carbon hydrogen), which can be used to reach the minimum shares in the respective part of the regulation. The regulation applied from 1 January 2024, except for articles 4, 5, 6, 8 and 10 which shall apply from 1 January 2025.²⁹

There is a consistency between the definition of RFNBO in the REDII/III and ReFuelEU aviation regulation, as well as GHG methodology and sustainability criteria.³⁰ Some of the other definitions may differ (e.g. low-carbon hydrogen).

4.5.5 The FuelEU Maritime initiative's relevance for CCU

As with ReFuelEU Aviation, the FuelEU Maritime initiative is a part of the Fit for 55 package and seeks to support the decarbonisation of the maritime sector. It will increase the share of renewable and low-carbon fuels upon its entry into force on 1 January 2025 (apart from articles 8 and 9 which applies from 31 August 2024), reducing the GHG intensity of fuels used by the shipping sector. The GHG intensity of fuels used will gradually decrease by 2% in 2025 to 80% in 2050 (Article 4 of the Regulation). The Regulation applies to vessels above 5000 gross tonnages calling at European ports.

Among other things, the Regulation includes a special incentive regime to support the uptake of RFNBO with a high decarbonisation potential and excludes fossil fuels from the Regulation's certification process. This is done in recognition that the production cost of RFNBO is much higher than the market price of conventional fuels, thus providing measures to ensure support and flexibility for the uptake of RFNBO (preamble, 26). Article 5(3) sets a target for RFNBOs: if the share of RFNBOs is less than 1% in 2031, a subtarget of 2% will apply for 2034. This does not apply if "there is evidence of insufficient production capacity and availability of RFNBO to the maritime sector, uneven geographical distribution or a too high price of those fuel" (Article 5(5)). RFNBO and RCF "that do not comply with the GHG emissions savings threshold set out in Article 25(2) of Directive (EU) 2018/2001 shall be considered to have the same emission factors as the least favourable fossil fuel pathway for that type of fuel." (Article 10). It is commonly understood that low-carbon fuels can also contribute to reaching the GHG reduction targets for the shipping sector established in the Regulation.

As detailed in 4.5.3, the use of the CCU fuels will be recognised in the EU ETS to avoid double counting the embodied carbon emissions (Industrial Carbon Management Strategy, 4.4).

4.5.6 Concluding remarks on the regulatory environment for CCU

There are currently several instruments that provide pieces of the regulatory puzzle for CCU, providing incentives and push for an uptake of CCU. As highlighted in the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy, CCU will play a key role to reach climate targets. Indeed, it provides

²⁹ European Council, 'RefuelEU initiative: Council adopts new law to decarbonise the aviation sector' aviation <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2023/10/09/refueleu-aviation-initiative-council-adopts-new-law-to-decarbonise-the-aviation-sector/>

³⁰ CO2 Value Europe, 'Position paper: CCU EU Policy Landscape' (February 2022) https://co2value.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/Position-paper_CVE_CCU-in-EU-Policy-Landscape_February-2022_FINAL.pdf

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that “up to a third” of 280Mt of CO₂ captured in 2040 will be utilised (p. 7), and up to 200Mt (45%) of the total of 450Mt CO₂ captured in 2050 will be utilised (p. 3), while the rest will be stored via CCS. However, for CCU to play a significant role in the EU economy, existing structural challenges, and regulatory barriers to the deployment of CCU technologies need to be identified and addressed (Industrial Carbon Management Strategy, 4.4). The EU has also worked on other legislations, which may help to support and deploy CCU projects at national level, for example the Net Zero Industry Act (NZIA) which considers CCU as a net zero technology, and considers CO₂ transport and utilisation as eligible to be qualified as strategic net zero projects at national level.

4.6 CCS Directive Operationalisation Challenges

The EU Directive 2009/31/EC on the geological storage of carbon dioxide and any amending Directives provide a legal framework for the safe geological storage of CO₂ in the EEA, which also holds implications for MRV and accounting (European Commission n.d). Of relevance to the reliability of MRV and the risk of leakage (reversal), the Directive includes detailed provisions on the selection of storage sites and exploration permits, storage permits and the operation and ultimate closure of storage sites – stating for example that geological storage sites “shall have no significant risk of leakage and shall not pose any significant risks to the environment or health”. Furthermore, any storage site shall be operated with a dedicated storage permit, with only one operator being allowed to use each storage site. It also provides for a post-closure monitoring period and transfer of responsibility and liability from the storage site operator to a national authority that is to be established or designated by the MS. According to Article 19 of the EU CCS Directive, the storage operators are expected to cover “at least the anticipated cost of monitoring for the period of 30 years” and ensure that the CO₂ is ‘completely and permanently contained in geological storage sites after the transfer of responsibility.’ (EU 2009).

The Directive also regulates third-party access to transportation networks and storage sites, asking MS to ensure that third parties can access these networks and storage sites. Such joint infrastructure around hubs, clusters and networks and subsequent issues around cross-border transport and dedicated MRV will likely become more relevant in the future.

The CCS Directive requires that sometime after closure (to be determined by the competent authority, but at least 20 years) the responsibility for a CO₂ storage site can be transferred from the operator to the competent authority.

Differences in MS operationalisation of the storage directive cause economic uncertainty, especially regarding cases of bankruptcies before transferral to national authorities.

Storage operators are required to provide financial security (or an equivalent, as determined by the competent authority) to ensure that all obligations under the directive can be met, including taking corrective measures to address and leakages and paying and surrendering EU ETS emissions trading allowances for any escaped CO₂. This has economic implications and any ambiguities (e.g. in permitting processes) can cause problems for economic viability.

4.7 Issues to be addressed in private sector contracts between value-chain partners

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Given their international responsibilities – for example in case of transactions under the Paris Agreement to fully address reversals when they occur – national regulators will be expected to put in place regulations or permitting provisions that impose penalties on private operators of CO₂ transport and storage sites in case of leakages. If national legislation – or permitting provisions – foresee compensation requirements in case of leakage and other disturbances in CCUS value chains – there may need for private sector contractual provisions that specify the associated burden among value-chain partners if leakage and other disturbances happen to appropriately share the cost-implications among capture, transport, and storage providers. For this it may be important to consider examples from carbon market standard setters, which have developed instruments to regulate any financial harm arising from leakage (e.g. Verra’s non-permanence risk tool for geological storage).

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5 Focus Regions

CCUS ZEN focusses on two regions that are at an early stage of considering CCUS especially when compared to the North Sea Region: the Baltic Sea Region and the Mediterranean Sea Region. This affords opportunities for drawing on knowledge and best practices from the North Sea region to facilitate development of CCUS. However, regional differences will also need to be considered as they can pose challenges requiring regional solutions – across the non-technical issues outlined regarding acceptance, political, economic, MRV and accounting, and legal dimensions.

Our consideration of regional specificities draws on the identification and involvement of relevant end users, public authorities and societal stakeholders through an online survey eliciting responses from regional actors within the project network, and three online workshop-style webinars encouraging further engagement with regional actors.

5.1 Baltic Sea Region

The Baltic Sea Region focus countries are Germany, Denmark, and Sweden (see section 1.1.3) though in the following we explore also other countries in the region. We examine narratives and public perceptions, the levels of regulatory support, the status and applicability of international regulations and their economic circumstance insofar they may impact on non-technical success factors.

5.1.1 Finland

Finland's largest emission sources are the pulp and paper industries and thermal power and heat plants, which are located at coastal as well as inland sites. For instance, Helsinki's industrial cluster emits about 6.5 million tonnes of CO₂ from refineries, power, and chemicals industries. Currently, the revised Finnish Climate Act (423/2022) includes a Medium-term Climate Change Plan, and it aims to reach carbon neutrality by 2035. One of the most prominent programs in Finland is the Sustainable Growth Programme, which invests in hydrogen and CCU (carbon capture and utilisation) projects with EUR 150 million. Further, pilot projects for waste incineration with CCUS will take place, while research and development for carbon management (e.g., carbon use and removals) have been carried out.

However, as Finland does not have suitable geologic formations for CO₂ storage, Finland sees opportunities for the Danish potential storage site of Rødby with its storage capacity of 242 to 449 million tonnes of CO₂ and the possibility of using the existing shipping line. Other opportunities could be in the Eastern Baltic Sea Region such as Latvia. A paper, which was published by Pihkola *et al.* in 2017, identifies that the lack of storage potential is one of the key barriers for enabling CCS along with other barriers such as the high price of CCS and a lack of concrete investment plans.

With the acknowledgement that there are no suitable geological formations for storage, Finland only allows storage for less than 100,000 tons of CO₂ for research, development, or demonstration purposes. Yet, in the Finnish document for transposing the CCS Directive, it leaves room for re-evaluation of the use of geological storage of CO₂ within its territory.

To capture CO₂ from facilities, environmental permits should be obtained from the Finnish government. The operators should not only ensure the quality requirements for CO₂ streams

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and other obligations for capturing CO₂ are met under the CCS Directive throughout the capturing process, but also complete additional analysis of the composition of the CO₂ stream and a risk assessment. Further, recording the data about the CO₂ streams is necessary. For transporting CO₂, the Finnish Energy Authority can intervene in authorising CO₂ capture entities to access a transport network in case of disputes with transport network entities based on the CCS Directive.

Finland is a Contracting Party to the London Protocol and has accepted the 2009 amendment, but not deposited a declaration of provisional application to the IMO. If Finland wants to export their CO₂ to other states where the storage site is offshore, Finland needs to provisionally apply the 2009 amendment. Status of membership to the London Protocol for the receiving country will impact the legal requirements that Finland has to adhere to under the Protocol. If Finland exports CO₂ to e.g., Denmark, Article 6.2 mandates an arrangement or agreement that identifies and allocates permitting responsibilities. If Finland wishes to export to a non-Contract Party, e.g., Poland, the agreement or arrangement shall include provisions at a minimum equivalent to the provisions contained in the London Protocol. Finland is also a party to the Helsinki Convention, the only implication here is that the Baltic Sea Area is not open for storage which does not impact Finland beyond potential R&D as the national framework prohibits storage.

5.1.2 Poland

In Poland, most of its emissions is coming from fossil fuels including coal. In Northern Poland, the region is divided into two clusters of emission sources: Gdańsk-Pomerania (north) and Kuyavia-Masovia (south), which emit about 9Mt/yr and 13.6Mt/yr respectively. Most of the emitters in the energy sector use biomass co-firing with varying degrees.

Poland's national energy policy by 2040 briefly mentions CCUS and clean coal technologies. CCUS is often discussed as a subset of Clean Coal Technologies (CCT) or blue hydrogen technologies. In 2021, Polish Minister of Climate and Environment appointed an advisory board, the Team on Development of CCUS technologies, where representatives of government, industry and research organisations were invited to facilitate implementation of CCUS technologies in Poland. The CCUS Working Group is involved in the feasibility study for CCS facilities in the energy sector, the cement sector, and other industrial sectors (Ministry of Climate and Environment Poland n.d.).

There is no official government backed strategy or roadmap on implementation of CCUS. Current law allows CO₂ storage for demonstration projects within offshore area in the Northeast part of Polish Baltic sector, however such activities are prohibited under the Helsinki Convention to which Poland is party to. There are some limitations and regulatory barriers to onshore storage, but forthcoming amendments to CCS regulations are expected to address these issues (CCS4CEE n.d.). This includes allowing for projects of a commercial nature. The project, "Poland-EU CCS Interconnector", with the industrial cluster in Gdańsk, has been partly funded by the EU Innovation Fund Lafarge CCS project of Kujawy cement plant.

5.1.3 Western Baltic Sea Region: Denmark, Sweden, Germany

In Denmark, the political support for CCUS projects is relatively strong with investments through subsidies. Denmark plays an important role for CO₂ storage for the North Sea and Baltic Sea regions with its potential of providing 12 to 22 billion tonnes of CO₂ storage.

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Sweden has recognised CCS as a means to achieving negative emissions, especially through BECCS. 85% of its emissions are envisaged to be cut through emission reduction while the remaining 15% should be covered by additional measures such as CCS. CCS is supported by Swedish policy measures such as investment and the regulatory framework in development.

The CCS Directive was transposed in 2014, mainly through the Swedish Environmental Act (1998:808) and the Swedish Continental Shelf Act (1966:314). The specific rules regarding geological storage of CO₂ were implemented in the regulation (2014:21) of geological storage of CO₂. The Regulation has been updated on several occasions (CO₂GeoNet, State-of-Play on CO₂ Geological Storage in 32 European Countries, 2021). Commercial scale storage is permitted offshore. The Regulation does not apply to project involving storage under 100kt, which can also be done onshore. Such projects have to fulfil the requirements contained in the Swedish Environmental Act.

Germany is considered one of Europe's largest emitters and aims to become climate neutral by 2050. Therefore, CCS is considered unavoidable. Germany is preparing a subsidy programme for the raw material industry to develop CCUS technologies. Germany is not actively pursuing the development of storage sites on national territory, partially due to public scrutiny and opposition to it. Current German law does not allow for storage as the deadline for applications on CO₂ storage ended December 31st 2016. The legislation is under revision to facilitate for transport infrastructure. Therefore, CO₂ export is considered very likely.

The most prominent storage sites mapped for CO₂ injection are in Denmark. These include onshore, nearshore, and offshore structures. GEUS and Energistyrelsen advanced the potential availability of 12 to 22 billion tonnes of CO₂ storage in Denmark. Denmark is also internationally recognised for the progress in establishing a legal framework for CO₂ storage and supporting the repurposing the depleted oil and gas fields into permanent shelters for CO₂. While they have a framework for offshore storage in place, the onshore legal framework is under development.

All these countries are parties to the London Protocol and the OSPAR Convention. Where Denmark and Sweden have deposited declarations of provisional application under the London Protocol and entered into separate MoUs, Germany has not done so yet or accepted the 2009 amendment. In the 2023 country report on the implementation of the CCS Directive, Germany stated that they are "currently discussing the suggested ratification of the change to the Article 6 London Protocol to allow the export of CO₂ for the purpose of onshore storage". It is not clear whether they are referring to accepting the 2009 amendment or depositing a declaration of provisional application – though it seems that they are referring to the act of accepting the 2009 amendment. They will also need to submit a declaration of provisional application before export can occur. It should also be noted that while Germany referred to onshore storage, it is likely they meant offshore storage – as the London Protocol has no bearing on onshore storage operations.

5.1.4 Eastern Baltic Sea Region: Estonia, Latvia, and Lithuania

The largest CO₂ emissions in Lithuania are produced by five plants including Achema chemical plant, Orlen refineries, Akmenes Cement and two power plants in Vilnius. The largest CO₂ emissions in Latvia are produced by four plants including Schwenk Latvia cement plant

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and three power plants located near Riga. In Estonia four power plants and three shale oil plants in the North-East of Estonia, where shale oil for energy and oil production is used, are the leading CO₂ emitters (Shogenova et al, 2023).

Estonia, Latvia, and Lithuania are in the common Baltic Sedimentary Basin and the best CO₂ storage capacity and geological conditions for gas storage (e.g., Deimena Formation sandstones of the Cambrian Series 3) are available in Latvia. Storage capacity estimated earlier was about 400 Mt onshore and 300 Mt of CO₂ offshore (Šilaupa 2013). The largest onshore CO₂ storage capacity is available in North-Blidene and Dobeles structures. The largest CO₂ storage capacity offshore is available in the E6 structure offshore Latvia (Shogenova et al, 2023).

At a regional level, among the Eastern Baltic Sea countries, only Estonia is a member of the London Protocol and has accepted the 2009 amendment. Estonia has not yet submitted a declaration of provisional application.

However, geological storage is prohibited in all three countries. These countries are all Parties to the Helsinki Convention which prohibits storage of CO₂ in the Baltic Sea, which consequently also impacts their option to potentially open for storage in the future, at least offshore.

In Lithuania, CO₂ storage was originally permitted but was subsequently banned in 2019. In Estonia, such regulations were implemented based on the lack of suitable CO₂ geological storage sites. Only research purposes would allow CO₂ injection in Latvia and Estonia. Nevertheless, the process of adjusting climate strategy, policy, and CCS regulations is ongoing in Latvia, initiated by the largest CO₂ producers such as Latvenergo and Schwenk Latvia. That said, the draft bill of the new Climate Law makes clear that the ban on storage stays in place for the time being. Three of the largest onshore and offshore storage sites in Latvia have the capacity to store all large Estonian, Latvian, and Lithuanian fossil and bio-CO₂ emissions. All together 15.1 Mt of fossil and bio-CO₂ could be captured, transported, used, and stored, while only 13.7 Mt of fossil CO₂ produced annually (Shogenova et al, 2023).

Further, instead of paying about 1.4 billion Euro taxes for the fossil CO₂ production (at a cost of 100 Euro per t), the countries can use them for the implementation of climate targets and will additionally earn money for the negative emissions and storage projects. Additional revenues will come from geothermal energy recovery in Latvia, CO₂ mineral carbonation in Estonia and hydrogen production and storage in the Baltic CCUS clusters. The proposed transboundary CCUS cluster projects could create thousands of new jobs, save 10 times more existing jobs, and will support hydrogen production and storage projects.

5.2 Mediterranean Sea Region

The Mediterranean Sea Region also holds important potential for CCUS hubs and clusters, notably through the concentration of CO₂ sources in numerous port regions representing potentially attractive clusters and the associated opportunity for interlinking them with storage hubs in geologically suited areas.

5.2.1 Easter Mediterranean Sea: Türkiye and Greece

Türkiye has its emission sources mostly along the coast, including the industrial clusters in the Aegean and Marma regions. The clusters have thermal power plants, iron and steel factories,

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cement facilities and refineries. Yet, the storage sites are in a different part of the country, where hydrocarbon fields and regulations exist just for the use of CO₂ for EOR. The transportation of CO₂ from the Marmara region to the storage sites would require ships to pass through the Canakkale Strait to reach the Aegean Sea. WP1 D1.2 suggests that the more convenient path from İzmir Aliğa to the basins located in Greece would be preferred if the cross-border CO₂ storage is coordinated. Greece has large saline aquifers and the Prinos Basin with its nearly depleted oil field may hold significant capacity potential though no specific areas have been officially designated yet.

Türkiye does not have any legal requirements or ETS mechanisms for industrial players to reduce CO₂ emissions, while the monitoring and reporting of CO₂ emissions by the specified companies stated in the legislations is mandatory. Türkiye does not have a regulatory framework in place that regulates CCS activities. Thus, storage is neither prohibited nor regulated. As Türkiye is not an EU Member State, it is under no obligation to transpose the CCS Directive. If Türkiye decides to regulate this activity, it is likely to follow the requirements of the CCS Directive given its aspirations of EU accession. Türkiye is not a Contracting Party to the London Protocol.

The CCS Directive was transposed into Greek law by Ministerial Decision 48416/2037/2011. In their 2023 country report on the implementation of the CCS Directive, Greece noted that Article 173 of L.4964/2022 introduced “a new licensing process for CO₂ exploration and storage permits for economical operators who already hold hydrocarbon exploration and production rights in areas which could potentially be used for carbon storage.”

Greece is also not a Contracting Party to the London Protocol. The implication of this is that Türkiye and Greece are not bound by the requirements of the London Protocol, and no Article 6.2 arrangement or agreement will be needed.

Greece is a Contracting Party to the Barcelona Convention and has ratified the 1976 Dumping Protocol and would need to issue permits in line with the provisions of those instruments. Greece is not a party to 1995 Dumping Protocol as of yet.

5.2.2 Italy

Based on Italy's National Energy and Climate Plan, the country set its national targets to 2030 in line with the 2030 EU Climate and Energy Package. It aims to reduce EU-wide net GHG emissions by 40% from 1990 levels. Italy plans to update its National Energy and Climate Plan in 2023 and align it with the enhanced EU targets to achieve the new -55% target.

Italy has planned to launch CCS projects and storage sites for the last decades although it does not have any full-scale projects until now. One of the projects that have made progress is the Brindisi CCS project in southern Italy, which was evaluated by Enel and ENI, but it discontinued in 2016.

Currently, the country is planning to launch its first CCS Hub project, called the Ravenna Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) project in northeast Italy by with Eni and Sam as operators. The aim is to transport carbon through pipelines from a natural gas treatment plant and store it in a depleted gas field. Initial partners of the CCS hub project will come from the power sector. Consequently, industrial players such as those from the steel, chemicals, ceramics, cement and waste sectors will also join.

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Italy transposed the CCS Directive with Decree No. 162/2011, which has later been amended, most recently with a new Energy Decree.³¹ Italy allows for storage in all areas except for seismically active areas, in the water column and the areas affected by aquifers whose eaters can have a drinkable or irrigated use. Italy is a Contracting Party to the London Protocol, the Barcelona Convention and the 1995 and 1976 Dumping Protocols and would need to issue the relevant permits in line with these instruments. If the 1995 Dumping Protocol to the Barcelona Convention enters into force unamended (without CO₂ being added as an exception to the ban), storage would be prohibited.

5.2.3 Southern France

In the Southern France and the North-eastern Europe, there are possibilities that CCUS hub projects can take place. In France, Marseille is one of the largest cities in France with its main trading seaport and industrial cluster in Fos-sur-Mer, which plans to ship CO₂ to offshore storage sites in Italy.

Many industrial sites are in proximity and around the Etang de Berre. Lyon is another big city in the region with its chemistry industry. In these regions, there is a strong willingness for industry decarbonisation and proactive stakeholders with potential plans on hydrogen. There have been discussions on hydrogen infrastructure development from Spain to Marseille along the Rhone Valley.

CO₂ geological storage is governed by the French Environmental Code which transposed the CCS Directive. The Environmental Code and the Mining Code together define the regulatory framework for the subsurface industry (CO₂GeoNet, State-of-Play on CO₂ Geological Storage in 32 European Countries, 2021). Storage of CO₂ is currently permitted onshore and offshore without specific limitations.

France is a Contracting Party to the London Protocol, the OSPAR Convention, the Barcelona Convention and the 1995 and 1976 Dumping Protocols. However, as the proposed storage site is onshore, and the CO₂ will be captured and transported within the French borders these instruments will have no implications.

5.2.4 Western Mediterranean Sea: Spain and France

In Spain, the industrial area around Tarragona and Barcelona has the highest CO₂ emissions in Spain. The Barcelona cluster has 14 carbon-emitting sites, totalling 4.7Mt of annual CO₂ emissions, which include power, cement, and chemicals sectors. The Tarragona cluster is on the Mediterranean shore with 11 carbon-emitting sites, including refineries, power, and the chemical industry.

In Spain, CO₂ storage is regulated by Law 40/2010 which transposed the CCS Directive. Storage is permitted onshore and offshore, and in the 2023 country report on the implementation of the CCS Directive, Spain confirms that “there is no limitation to select areas if the geological formation chosen as a storage site – under the proposed conditions of use – has no significant risk of leakage and no significant risk to the environment or human health.”

³¹ The Italian Government approved Law Decree No. 181/2023 on 9 December 2023, which was converted with amendments into Law No. 11 of 2 February, 2024.

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The suggested storage site is within the geographical scope of the Barcelona Convention and not the OSPAR Convention. Spain is a Contacting Party to the London Protocol, the Barcelona Convention and the 1995 and 1976 Dumping Protocols and will have to issue permits for storage according to the aforementioned instruments. If the 1995 Dumping Protocol to the Barcelona Convention enters into force unamended, storage would be prohibited. France and Spain would need to enter into a bilateral arrangement or agreement under the London Protocol.

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6 Conclusion

Non-technical challenges for the development of Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage (CCUS) hubs and clusters can individually hinder success and only jointly enable it. Success across the different dimensions seems a prerequisite to overall success: Regulatory, economic, and monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV) frameworks, along with legal and contractual structures. These must all align to pave the way for operational CCUS networks. Public perception and policy support are the linchpins in this complex mechanism.

Firstly, the readiness of regulatory frameworks and public acceptance are significant hurdles. As observed in the Baltic case, these factors can elongate the timeline to operational status. In regions like France and Spain, where emissions clusters are highly concentrated, the potential for economies of scale is substantial. Yet, this advantage may be offset by intricate permitting processes, potentially leading to project delays and escalated costs.

Secondly, political and regulatory uncertainties pose a substantial barrier, particularly noticeable in countries such as Germany, where the potential for carbon storage faces regulatory impediments and conflicting signals at national versus regional levels. These open issues are symptomatic of a broader hesitation to fully endorse CCS strategies, which in turn stifles the progress and realization of the technology's potential.

Thirdly, infrastructure concerns, particularly regarding the scale of transport networks like pipelines, present another layer of complexity. If not addressed, these uncertainties could lead to inflated CCS costs as projects may have to resort to more expensive alternatives for CO₂ transportation. Such logistical inefficiencies could significantly dampen the cost-effectiveness of CCS initiatives.

Fourthly, while there is a relatively advanced potential for carbon capture and storage, the situation for utilization remains less coordinated. This imbalance highlights the need for a more harmonized approach to harness the full spectrum of CCUS capabilities, ensuring that each aspect can progress in tandem to optimize the overall efficacy of the system.

Finally, the Danish storage sites present a beacon of promise, given the balance of CO₂ volumes and the significant emissions from the German economy. The accessibility of these sites, encompassing logistical, institutional, and contractual facets, is critical for ensuring timely and efficient delivery. It is this intricate web of factors that will determine the success or failure of CCUS hubs and clusters, underscoring the need for a concerted effort to address these non-technical challenges with as much rigor as the technical ones.

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